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**Who Owns What in Fanfiction:
Perceptions of Ownership and Problems
of Law**

by

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Abstract

Online fanfiction is at the forefront of the conflict between copyright holders and fans who wish to use the material of the mass culture for their own purposes. Fans feel that their fan status and non-profit use of the material cannot cause any harm, whilst copyright holders feel they have to protect their property and livelihood from dilution and misuse. As a consequence of this standoff, many fans have received threats of legal action should they continue to use copyrighted material.

This article analyses the relevant American and British copyright laws and highlights the various legal defences that could be used to argue for the legality of fanfiction. It also explores the attitudes of copyright holders towards fanfiction and looks into what legal action has been taken against fanfiction writers. A survey of 200 fans then explores the fans' perspective and attempts to determine why fans write fanfiction and how they have responded to the legal activity against them.

It concludes that whilst fanfiction has a relatively strong legal position should the matter ever come before a court of law, this is unlikely in the current situation as both sides fear they have too much to lose. It also concludes that the current system of copyright law is too rigid and inflexible for the fast-paced, rapidly changing computer age in which we live.

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Introduction

In recent years terms such as ‘intellectual property rights’ and ‘copyright infringement’ have become more and more commonplace, evidence of a shift in perception of copyright law from a legal instrument designed to promote the common good and encourage creativity to a conception of ideas as sacrosanct under natural law. As a result of this shift copyright law is being increasingly expanded to protect the rights of copyright holders without a corresponding protection of public interest. Critics argue that the current expansion of copyright law is a form of intellectual protectionism and is designed to serve the interests of large media corporations without regard for society’s interest.

Almost every day there are news articles about music and film piracy and not a month goes by without some form of legal challenge being launched against fan-based copyright infringement, ranging from *The X-Files* fan sites to fan-created English-language subtitles for Japanese manga cartoons. Whilst the attention of media corporations is primarily directed against the large-scale piracy rings centred in the Far East, they are increasingly turning their attention to the perceived illegal activity of their fans. In 1997, for example, Warner Brothers launched a legal challenge against a website run by a 15-year-old *Harry Potter* fan.

Despite the apparent harmlessness of the fans’ activity, in almost all of these cases there is a clearly defined basis in law for the copyright holder’s actions. A fan site containing video clips and images from the *Harry Potter* films is infringing copyright, however harmless the intent behind it. Publishing fan-made subtitles for manga, especially when there is already an official source licensed by the creators, is infringing copyright.

Making a profit from copying and using tangible copyrighted material such as digital media without permission is clearly illegal copyright infringement and the media corporations in particular are becoming hyper-vigilant about protecting their interests in these cases. However, there is a particular form of creative fan

activity online where the law is not quite so clear-cut, where in fact the law is almost silent, and that is fanfiction.

For much of its history fanfiction has been very much an underground movement, conducted through self-published 'fanzines' and involving limited numbers of participants. With its ease of self-publication and access, the Internet has allowed millions of budding writers to publish their stories online and the numbers are growing every year. It is this explosive growth, which can no longer remain underground, that has brought fanfiction to the attention of both academics and copyright holders, with all the resultant advantages and disadvantages therein.

Whilst the issues of copyright and intellectual property rights have grown in prominence in recent years, especially when related to the Internet, the legal debate has still largely been occupied by media piracy, no doubt because this form of copyright infringement has immediate financial repercussions for those involved. Because fanfiction is seen as a fairly recent phenomenon (although as mentioned its roots go back at least thirty years, if not longer) and because it does not involve money, it therefore still occupies a fairly uncertain legal position. Any arguments relating to the legality or lack thereof of fanfiction have to rely on the overlapping penumbra of a number of different issues, none of which specifically relate to fanfiction.

A large proportion of academics writing on the subject argue that fanfiction is in fact not illegal and should be definitively protected by law, and that the current system of copyright law has become too inflexible and too bound to servicing the needs of major corporate copyright holders without allowing for the need of cultural creativity.

As a result of its underground and community-based status, fanfiction writers themselves have been given very little opportunity to make their opinions known on this subject. This thesis is designed to rectify that: to examine the relevant legal arguments that can be brought both against and on behalf of fanfiction, to explore the differing viewpoints on either side of the fanfiction divide, and to try

and explain why fanfiction writers persist in indulging in creative activity that may find them on the receiving end of a legal challenge from a major media corporation.

Aims & Objectives:

This dissertation aims to investigate the perceptions of ownership – legal ownership on the one side and emotional on the other – that has led fanfiction to a legal impasse and to determine whether the various legal defences that can be brought to bear on the behalf of fans in this case are strong enough to argue for a categorical legal exception for fanfiction under copyright law.

In order to adequately discuss the issue of fanfiction and its uncertain legal position, some background information is first needed. Chapter 1 begins with an attempt to define what exactly fanfiction is, before proceeding to investigate its history, origins, structure and source material. The chapter is then concluded by a review of the literature previously written on the subject.

This is then followed in Chapter 2 by an introduction to legal problems relating to fanfiction, in particular the legal uncertainties surrounding the issue and lack of available case law, before moving into a more in depth look at the relevant sections of US and UK copyright law and the various legal arguments that can be used to defend fanfiction.

Chapter 3 explores the attitudes and actions of the copyright holders – the publishers, media corporations and authors – many of whom feel that fanfiction is a blatant infringement of copyright. It investigates the varying viewpoints of those involved, both positive and negative, before going on to examine what legal action has been taken and what the consequences were.

Chapter 4 looks at the issue from a fanfiction writer's point-of-view, examining the opinions of fanfiction writers, through a widespread survey of the fanfiction community, in an attempt to determine what legal awareness these individuals have; how they attempt to regulate their own actions within the fanfiction community; what damage limitations they have in place to deflect legal

attention; and why they persist in writing fanfiction that may result in them facing a legal challenge.

Finally, the dissertation concludes that fanfiction's own success has led to the current legal scrutiny and that it is unlikely to go away, despite the legal intimidation. It also debates whether current copyright law is serving the interests of culture and concludes that current copyright is too rigid and inflexible.

Methodology:

The research required for this study was broken down into three distinct areas – a comprehensive literature review, a close study of the relevant UK and US copyright laws and related pertinent cases, and a survey of members of the fanfiction community. Since the study of fanfiction is still a rather overlooked aspect of the overall discipline of media studies, there are very few examples of research on which this study could be based. As a result the research followed a somewhat exploratory pattern, especially concerning the survey, and should further study be undertaken the technique may be refined.

Literature Review

The literature review comprised the first stage of this study, before any hypotheses or suppositions were formed. Academic texts were identified through a keyword search of a variety of databases and catalogues. Google Scholar also proved useful in detecting articles, as did a general search using the main Google search engine. It was through the latter that one of the most useful tools in identifying literature on the subject was discovered: a regularly updated bibliography created by two authors of a study of fanfiction, Karen Hellekson and Kristina Busse.

Those texts that appeared pertinent and useful were then read and thematically summarised, with arguments and themes that were found to be repeated noted for further examination. The work of Henry Jenkins was found to be particularly useful in this respect.

Fanfiction is still regarded as something of a niche subject within the larger field of media studies and the available literature on the subject is therefore somewhat limited. Many of the academic texts that were identified did not prove relevant to this study, having an academic focus that was not applicable: a feminist study of female fanfiction writers, for example, or the use of fanfiction as a means of

expressing taboo sexualities. Very few texts on fanfiction even mentioned the legal aspect and those that did tended to do so only in passing.

In addition, not all academic texts were available to this researcher, for reasons of access and cost, among others. The literature review therefore is not as comprehensive as it ideally could be.

Legal Analysis

Whilst there are great similarities and differences in much international copyright law, for the purposes of this dissertation the aim was to focus on two particular countries which between them contribute a large proportion of fanfiction online. As will be mentioned subsequently, there is a great deal of online fanfiction based on Japanese manga/anime, which obviously falls under Japanese copyright law. Japanese copyright law is greatly more tolerant of derivative and unofficial works than the copyright laws of the US and UK, and since the purpose of this study was to focus on the conflict between copyright holders and fanfiction writers a close study of Japanese law was not deemed relevant.

The US 1976 Copyright Act and the UK 1988 Copyrights, Designs and Patents Act were both closely examined in order to determine the exact wording of the laws and to identify the various exceptions that are included and could be applied to fanfiction. The exceptions and their applicability to fanfiction were then studied and the various cases that have been brought pertaining to such exceptions identified and scrutinized for potential parallels with fanfiction. Many of these cases were identified via articles on the various aspects of copyright laws found through keyword search on databases such as Lexus-Nexis.

Survey

The survey used a combination of qualitative and quantitative questioning – generally a quantitative question was first asked, with a limited number of

available answers, and then a subsequent qualitative response was required, explaining the choice of answer. Participants were also presented with a number of statements with which they were given the option to agree or disagree at varying levels. The aim was to draw out opinions on and knowledge of fanfiction and copyright – statistics, whilst useful, were not the primary goal.

A pilot study was first undertaken using a randomly selected number of fanfiction authors. Twenty-five e-mail addresses were taken from a selection of stories, chosen again at random, from Fanfiction.net and requests were sent for participation. Of these, 13 responded. These participants were asked to take the survey and were then interviewed via e-mail and online messenger in order to gauge their opinions. As a result of this pilot study, a number of questions which were deemed irrelevant were excluded, some questions were clarified and/or expanded and several new questions were inserted.

A request for new participants was then posted on a number of online fanfiction communities chosen at random through a Google search, including forums, message boards and blog communities. No incentive was proffered for involvement and participants were not required to provide any personal details, save a name or pseudonym for use should any of their responses be quoted and an e-mail address should any follow-up interviews be required. The survey itself was hosted on an online survey construction website and a link provided in each request post. At the end of the survey participants were provided with the URL for a website where the results and ensuing dissertation would be posted upon completion.

The original aim was to get at least 50 responses but the response proved to be greater than anticipated and the eventual number of responses reached 200. As a result of this number and the thoroughness and lucidity of many of the responses follow-up interviews were not deemed necessary.

There are of course limitations to this approach. The participants do not represent a true random sample: in posting a general invitation rather than specifically selecting randomly chosen individuals the end outcome was a self-selecting

sample. It is likely that writers without at least background knowledge of the basics of copyright law would have avoided taking the survey and those who were more informed would have inevitably left longer and more detailed responses. In addition, the survey clearly only targets and includes English-language speakers, whilst a great number of fanfiction writers do not write in English. However, considering the particular laws focussed on both stem from countries in which English is the official language this particular limitation was not deemed a problem.

Chapter 1

Background

1.1 Defining Fanfiction

Defining fanfiction is not as easy as it may first appear. In its most accepted definition, the term ‘fanfiction’, also written as fan fiction and often abbreviated to fanfic or fic, refers to stories most commonly based upon films, television programs and novels, written by fans of the original material and incorporating characters and settings that the fans did not create. However, this is a rather broad definition and can just as easily be applied to many works of literature as it can to unofficial creative fan activity.

In fact, despite appearances to the contrary, there is arguably not a great deal of difference between what is generally considered to be fanfiction and a lot of published literature. If fanfiction is derivative then so are a great number of published novels, including some classics of English literature such as Jean Rhys’ *Wide Sargasso Sea* or George MacDonald Fraser’s *Flashman* series. If fanfiction defies the canon (the officially sanctioned characters, narrative and plot, as opposed to the ‘fanon’ creations of fans) of many television shows or films, then so do many licensed tie-in novels, some of which go so far as to explicitly contradict or rewrite the original canon. If fanfiction is not officially licensed, neither is *The Wind Done Gone*, a companion novel to Margaret Mitchell’s *Gone with the Wind* that was recently permitted publication by the US Court of Appeals, despite the lack of consent from the Mitchell Estate. And if fanfiction is written by fans, so are many television and film tie-in novels – in a discussion in the Livejournal community ‘supernatural_tv’ concerning his forthcoming *Supernatural* novel, writer Keith DeCandido says “because I am a fan of the show I jumped at it [the chance to write the novel]. And I had a great deal of fun writing it.”¹

¹ DeCandido, Keith. Comment in *Nevermore excerpt now up!* discussion thread in supernatural_tv Livejournal community.
<http://community.livejournal.com/supernatural_tv/1025168.html?thread=19885200#t19885200>, [24.05.07], [accessed 29.05.07]

As Teresa Nielson Hayden writes,

“In a purely literary sense, fanfic doesn’t exist. There is only fiction. Fanfic is a legal category created by the modern system of trademarks and copyrights. Putting that label on a work of fiction says nothing about its quality, its creativity, or the intent of the writer who created it. The Pulitzer Prize for Fiction this year [2006] went to *March*, a novel by Geraldine Brooks, published by Viking. It’s a re-imagining of the life of the father of the four March girls in Louisa May Alcott’s *Little Women*. Can you see a particle of difference between that and a work of declared fanfiction? I can’t. I can only see two differences: first, Louisa May Alcott is out of copyright; and second, Louisa May Alcott, Geraldine Brooks, and Viking are dreadfully respectable.”²

So perhaps the best way to define fanfiction is to identify what it is not: it is not officially licensed or authorised; it is not professionally edited or published; it does not form part of any recognised canon; it is not written by professional writers, at least not in their professional capacity, although some, Meg Cabot and Lois McMaster Bujold, for example, have confessed to writing fanfiction ; it does not conform to the often rigid formats of professional literature - “novel, novella, short story...formats with very specific needs and requirements”³; and, perhaps most importantly, it is not for profit.

This then will be the definition used for the purposes of this dissertation – that fanfiction is unofficial, unauthorised, derivative, freeform, non-profit fiction written by fans of the original material. The whys and wherefores will come later.

² Hayden, Teresa Nielson. *Fanfic: Force of Nature*.
<<http://nielsenhayden.com/makinglight/archives/007464.html#007464>>, [25.04.06], [accessed 27.05.07]

³ DeCandido, Keith. *The Difference Between Fanfic and Profic*.
<<http://kradical.livejournal.com/868712.html>>, [06.04.07], [accessed 29.05.07]

1.2 Fanfiction to the Current Day

The first example of what arguably could be considered to be fanfiction occurred in 1614, when a still-unknown individual, writing under the pseudonym of Alonso Fernandez de Avellaneda, published an unauthorised sequel to the first volume of Cervantes' Don Quixote, entitled *Segundo tomo del ingenioso hidalgo Don Quijote de la Mancha* ('Second Book of the Ingenious Knight Don Quixote of La Mancha')⁴. This was of course before copyright as a legal concept was introduced – it would be almost another hundred years before the first law to protect the rights of authors, the 1709 Statute of Anne, would be passed.

Elizabeth Judge has written of eighteenth-century writing circles based upon the works of Jane Austen⁵, and later, by the turn of the 19th century, there were a number of parodies and revisions of Lewis Carroll's *Alice in Wonderland* created by authors as well known as E. Nesbitt and Frances Burnett. The character of Sherlock Holmes also appeared in a number of unofficial publications, the first as early as 1905 in Maurice Leblanc's *Sherlock Holmes Arrive Trop Tard*. From this it is clear that the concept of writing derivative works based on another author's creation is not a recent phenomenon.

In its current incarnation, however, fanfiction can be traced back fairly definitively to the late 1960s and the television show *Star Trek*. Published whilst the series was still in its first run on NBC in 1967, *Spoockanalia* was the first Star Trek fanzine. It contained a mixture of fanfiction, poetry, articles about the show and a letter from Leonard Nimoy, who played Science Officer Spock, wishing the editors luck. These early fanzines were a distinctly unprofessional affair, often written and drawn by hand, and passed around person-to-person. As a result most had a very limited circulation and fanzines and fanfiction did not really take off until the mid 1970s, when commercial photocopying and the new

⁴ Iffland, James. Do we really need to read Avellaneda? *Bulletin of the Cervantes Society of America* [online], 21(1), 2001. <<http://www.h-net.org/~cervantes/csa/artics01/iffland.pdf>>, [accessed 17.06.07]

⁵ Judge, Elizabeth. 'Eighteenth-Century Fan Fiction and Copyright Law', *Authors and Others* [podcast]. A Working Conference of the Society for Critical Exchange, April 20-23, 2006. <http://www.law.case.edu/centers/lta/content.asp?content_id=89>, [retrieved 27.07.07]

Star Trek conventions meant that a much larger audience could be reached. By this point the phenomenon of fanfiction and fanzines had spread beyond *Star Trek* to other fandoms such as *Space 1999* and *Star Wars*, although it was still largely contained within the science-fiction genre.

The first known 'slash' story was published in *Grup #3* in 1974, although it took several years before slash fanfiction became a recognised genre within the fanfiction community (slash refers to the '/' in Kirk/Spock and has come to mean any male/male pairing in a story). The 1970s also saw the first cease-and-desist letter, sent by Paramount Studios to a *Star Trek* fanzine entitled *Dreadnought Explorations*. The case was subsequently dropped when Paramount realised that the fanzine was not a professional publication.

In 1976 the first commercial anthology of fanfiction was published by Bantam Books with the full consent of Paramount, entitled *Star Trek: The New Voyages*. It contained eight stories written by fans previously published in *Star Trek* fanzines and included a foreword by *Star Trek* creator Gene Roddenberry. It was followed up by a subsequent edition entitled *The New Voyages 2* and established a trend for *Star Trek* fan anthologies that has continued to this day. Simon & Schuster, the official *Star Trek* tie-in novel publisher, runs a yearly contest for inclusion in the *Strange New Worlds* anthology, which is currently in its 10th edition. Many fans whose stories have been included in these anthologies have gone on to professional careers writing official *Star Trek* novels.

The invention of Usenet in 1980 allowed for Internet-based gatherings of fans and the wider electronic distribution of fanfiction, largely centred on bulletin boards and mailing lists. However, it wasn't until the advent of the World Wide Web in the early 1990s that fanfiction really took off online. Since then its growth has been explosive.

A Google search for 'fanfiction' lists over 6 million results. On 'Fanfiction.net', the largest of the many online fanfiction archives, there are forty thousand stories devoted to *The Lord of the Rings* and close to quarter of a million for *Harry Potter*! There are even well over two thousand stories based on the Bible! Whilst

English is the predominant language, there are over 30 different languages represented. The website itself receives over 3 million hits per day⁶ and is consistently among the 250 most visited websites globally⁷. Of course, 'Fanfiction.net' is only one of many fanfiction archives online. There are innumerable others: for *Harry Potter* there is FictionAlley and Lumos; for *Lord of the Rings* there is Henneth Anun; for *Buffy the Vampire Slayer* there is The Sandlot; and the list goes on.

It would be impossible to state with any certainty the number of stories or 'fanfics' available online at any given time – a conservative estimate could be anywhere between 2 and 20 million or even higher. Many authors in the fanfiction community tend to avoid communal archives, publishing their work on their own blogs or websites, making the total number also impossible to adequately quantify. What is certain is that fanfiction is a significant presence online and is not going away – indeed, the number of published stories is increasingly day by day.

1.3 Literature Review:

Whilst the study of media, culture and audience participation has grown in prominence over the past few decades, fanfiction is still regarded as something of a niche subject, largely dismissed and ignored by mainstream academia. A search of the Library of Congress' online catalogue, for example, reveals one solitary work listed – Karen Hellekson and Kristina Busse's *Fan Fiction and Fan Communities in the Age of the Internet*. A search of the British Library's catalogue has the same result.

The most comprehensive bibliography devoted to fanfiction⁸, incidentally compiled by the authors of the aforementioned 'solitary work', lists 216 items written over a period of more than 30 years, the vast majority of which are

⁶ Statbrain.com. <[http://www.statbrain.com/www.'Fanfiction.net'/>, \[2005\], \[accessed 09.05.07\]](http://www.statbrain.com/www.'Fanfiction.net'/)

⁷ Alexa.
<http://www.alexa.com/data/details/traffic_details?url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.fanfiction.net>, [2007], [accessed 09.05.07]

⁸ Hellekson, Karen & Busse, Kristina. *Fan fiction: a bibliography of critical works*.
<<http://www.karenhellekson.com/theorize/fanfic-bib.html>>, [26.03.07], [accessed 04.06.07]

articles rather than books. Of this number, almost half focus on the prevalence of slash amongst female fanfiction writers, an interesting topic in itself but not one that bears much relation to this dissertation. Much of the remaining works on fanfiction unfortunately tread the roughly the same ground, focusing on what it is and who writes it, without really exploring why it is written and how it fits into a wider cultural context. As far as the legal aspect goes, most literature on fanfiction does not even mention it, or if it does it warrants no more than a sentence or two on copyright infringement.

Amongst the fanfiction community itself it is a different matter. Fanfiction writers are often highly self-aware and there are a large number of online communities devoted to discussing issues of ‘meta fandom’, with discussions ranging from copyright and intellectual property rights to the etiquette of feedback and criticism. These communities are valuable resources to draw upon when investigating the varied opinions and legal awareness of the fanfiction community, but, as with most sources, there is a caveat, especially in relation to legal issues. Most of the participants in these discussions are not lawyers, although there is a Livejournal community called ‘fandom_lawyers’, populated by members of the fanfiction community who are either lawyers or have legal experience.

This gives rise to one of the fundamental problems in analysing fanfiction – which sources are the most reliable, an academic who is viewing the phenomenon from the outside or a member of the fan community itself? One of the few academics writing on fanfiction who can reliably be said to be both is Henry Jenkins, who describes himself as an ‘acafan’, a portmanteau word made up of ‘academic’ and ‘fan’. Jenkins was one of the first scholars to study audience participation in a media culture and is widely recognised as one of the experts in the field. His book *Textual Poachers*, published in 1992 and now considered a landmark publication in television studies, stands head and shoulders above the rest of the literature on fanfiction and is one of the few publications to focus on fanfiction as a cultural concept and its resultant relations with the media and consumer capitalism.

In *Textual Poachers* Jenkins heavily criticises the stereotypical view of fans, and particularly science-fiction fans, as ‘geeks’, mere passive absorbers of culture, fixated on detail and irrelevancies. Heavily influenced by Michel de Certeau’s theory of poaching from the book *The Practice of Everyday Life*, in which de Certeau examines the way individuals appropriate mass culture to suit and in some cases explain and inform their own existence, Jenkins applies this argument as a way of defending modern fans and their creative output, portraying them as pro-active constructors of an underground ‘alternative’ culture that ‘poaches’ and reworks the popular media for its own ends. This culture, he argues, can be seen as a contemporary folk culture⁹.

Both Jenkins and de Certeau argue that the very act of reading – and watching – alters the meaning of a text, because each individual brings something different to the material, a different interpretation. De Certeau writes that “every reading modifies its object...The reader takes neither the position of the author nor an author’s position. He invents in the text something different from what they intended. He detaches them from their (lost or accessory) origin. He combines their fragments and creates something unknown.”¹⁰ De Certeau was not talking about fanfiction, but he might as well have been.

Jenkins also discusses fanfiction in one of his more recent books, *Convergence Culture*, in which he argues that fanfiction is part of the “public re-emergence of grassroots creativity...[in which] everyday people take advantage of new technologies that enable them to archive, annotate, appropriate and recirculate media content.”¹¹ Once pushed underground by the rise of the mass media, this folk culture production process has been enabled by the Internet to “come out from behind closed doors...[representing] a visible, public threat to the absolute control the culture industries [have asserted] over their intellectual property.”¹²

Jenkins breaks the response of the media industry down into two groups, what he calls the ‘prohibitionists’ and the ‘collaborationists’. The first tend to be found

⁹ Jenkins, Henry. *Textual Poachers*, 1992.

¹⁰ De Certeau, Michel. *The Practice of Everyday Life*, 1988, p. 169.

¹¹ Jenkins, Henry. *Convergence Culture*, 2006, p. 136.

¹² *Ibid.*, p. 137.

within the traditional media companies (film, television and music), are the most antagonistic towards this new culture and are generally the instigators of most legal action against consumers, seeking to “regulate and criminalize many forms of fan participation”¹³. The collaborationists on the other hand generally represent the new media (the Internet, gaming and mobile phone industries) and are far more accessible and flexible towards fans, experimenting with “new approaches that see fans as important collaborators in the production of content and as grassroots intermediaries helping to promote the franchise.”¹⁴

The problem with investigating the legality of fanfiction, as Jenkins acknowledges, is that there is simply no precedent for such widespread, non-profit copyright infringement. There is no case law regarding fanfiction. Although the publishers and media corporations own the copyright and therefore feel that the law - such as it is - is on their side, that is not necessarily the case. There are valid arguments for the legality of fanfiction, and it is certainly interesting that in the few cases where fans have fought back against cease-and-desist letters and other forms of corporate legal pressure the fans have generally won. Jenkins feels that there is a “public right to cultural participation”¹⁵ and that “a right to participate might be abstracted from the combined rights listed in the First Amendment and the right to participate would include the right to respond meaningfully to core materials of your culture.”¹⁶

One of the few academics writing on fanfiction from a legal standpoint is Rebecca Tushnet, a law professor at Georgetown University. In several articles on the subject she explores the various defences that can be brought to bear on behalf of fans. In ‘Legal Fictions: Copyright, Fan Fiction, and a New Common Law’¹⁷ she argues that fanfiction ought to fall under the ‘fair use’ protection clause of copyright law, since “fanfiction involves the productive addition of

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 134.

¹⁴ *Ibid.* p. 134.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 189.

¹⁶ Jenkins, Henry. ‘Fan Fiction as Critical Commentary’, Confessions of an Aca/Fan. <http://www.henryjenkins.org/2006/09/fan_fiction_as_critical_commen.html>, [27.09.07], [accessed 21.06.07]

¹⁷ Tushnet, Rebecca. Legal Fictions: Copyright, Fan Fiction, and a New Common Law, *Loyola of Los Angeles Entertainment Law Journal*, 1997, 17(3), 651-686.

creative labor to a copyright holder's characters, it is non-commercial and it does not act as an economic substitute for the original copyrighted work.”¹⁸. She develops this further in ‘Copy This Essay: How Fair Use Doctrine Harms Free Speech and How Copying Serves It’¹⁹, arguing that the current draconian copyright laws harm freedom of speech and stifle creativity.

This is an argument echoed by Christina Ranon in her article ‘Honor Among Thieves: Copyright Infringement in Internet Fandom’. Ranon describes fanfiction as “a dialogue about the dominant culture between consumers and producers of creative products” and believes that as such it ought to be protected from litigation by a “categorical fair use exception”²⁰. So too in ‘Performance, Property, and the Slashing of Gender in Fan Fiction’ Sonia Katyal argues that copyright law needs to “equalize the authorial monopoly of the creator in favor of a more dialogic and dynamic relationship between producers and consumers in the process”²¹.

Rebecca Tushnet has also written, with Bruce Keller, about the parody exception to copyright law. In ‘Even More Parodic Than The Real Thing: Parody Lawsuits Revisited’, Tushnet and Keller caution that in future cases judges may find themselves passing ‘literary judgement’ on works, permitting the publication of works they find aesthetically acceptable and denying those that are not. They conclude that judges need to “take a broader view of transformation when they address humorous (and non-humorous) unauthorized use of works, marks or images.”²², exactly the kind of view that was taken by the US Court of Appeals in supporting the publication of *The Wind Done Gone*, a parallel novel to Margaret Mitchell’s *Gone with the Wind*.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 654.

¹⁹ Tushnet, Rebecca. Copy This Essay: How Fair Use Doctrine Harms Free Speech and How Copying Serves It, *Yale Law Journal*, 2005, 114(3), 535-592.

²⁰ Ranon, Christina. Honor Among Thieves, *Vanderbilt Journal of Entertainment and Tech Law*, 2006, 8(2), p. 451.

²¹ Katyal, Sonia. Abstract from Performance, Property, and the Slashing of Gender in Fan Fiction. *Journal of Gender, Social Policy, and the Law* [online], 2006, 14(3), p. 461-518. <<http://www.wcl.american.edu/journal/genderlaw/14/katyal3.pdf?rd=1>>, [accessed 15.07.07]

²² Tushnet, Rebecca & Keller, Bruce. Even More Parodic Than The Real Thing: Parody Lawsuits Revisited, *Trademark Reporter*, 2004, 94, p.1016.

Another argument that has been used to support fanfiction is that of implied consent, argued by Meredith McCardle²³ and Leanne Stendell²⁴ among others, in which if an author or other such copyright holder is aware of the existence of fanfiction and has made statements either supporting or not implicitly condemning it, then that author has implied consent and cannot subsequently bring an action for copyright infringement.

²³ McCardle, Meredith. Fandom, Fan Fiction, and Fanfare: What's All the Fuss?, *Boston University Journal of Science and Technology Law* [online], 2003, 9(2). <<http://www.bu.edu/law/central/jd/organizations/journals/scitech/volume92/mccardle.pdf>>, [accessed 03.05.07]

²⁴ Stendell, Leanne. Fanfic and Fan Fact: How Current Copyright Law Ignores the Reality of Copyright Owner and Consumer Interests in Fan Fiction, *SMU law review*, 2005, 58(4), 1551-1581.

Chapter 2

Copyright Law

2.1 The Nature of the Problem

It is largely the explosive growth of fanfiction online that has led to the current legal predicament; it was easy enough for fanfiction to remain underground when it was based on fanzines being passed hand-to-hand at small unofficial gatherings or conventions and the numbers involved did not rise above a few thousand at most. If the copyright holders involved were even aware of its existence at this time, such small-scale informal use of copyrighted material could hardly have seemed much of a threat. Indeed, the only occasion when a copyright holder moved to take legal action against fanfiction was when it felt that a profit was being made, as in the case of Paramount Studios and the *Dreadnought Explorations* fanzine, and once Paramount realised there were in fact no financial transactions taking place the suit was dropped. However, fanfiction has grown enormously since its early days and can no longer be ignored by ‘The Powers That Be’ or TPTB, as the major corporations tend to be referred to among fans.

Whilst the law can vary enormously around the world, the vast majority of fanfiction online falls under UK and US copyright law. There is nevertheless a substantial amount of art- and text-based fanfiction based on Japanese anime or manga, often referred to as *dōjinshi*. Under Japanese law, *dōjinshi* is not strictly legal; however, it is generally tolerated and even encouraged, largely on the basis that it keeps fans interested in the original material and provides a launching pad for artists and writers who may go on to professional careers. As Jennifer Granick writes,

“That it not only exists but thrives is a testament to Japan's relaxed attitudes on copyright, which have facilitated a flowering of both creative and commercial activity... when it comes to creating derivative works, the

commercial comic and anime companies look the other way. As a result there's consumption, but there's creativity too.”²⁵

Indeed, Sean Leonard has argued that *dōjinshi* is largely responsible for the recent rise in interest in Japanese manga and anime in the American market, despite it being largely abandoned by the Japanese copyright holders²⁶.

Copyright holders in the US and the UK are not so relaxed about protecting their copyrighted material. Fanfiction, unless it is based on works that are no longer or never were under copyright, such as the novels of Jane Austen or Shakespeare's plays, entails the use of copyrighted characters and fictional worlds without permission; as a result, many copyright holders perceive it to be copyright infringement and often threaten legal action accordingly, usually in the form of cease-and-desist (C&D) letters. Fans generally comply with these letters because they do not have the legal and financial clout to take on these copyright holders, who are often major multinational corporations.

Unfortunately, this tends to lend credence to the idea that the fans are in the wrong and 'The Powers That Be' have the law on their side, which is not necessarily the case, as we shall see. It is true that neither British nor American copyright law makes a specific exception for fanfiction, as they do for educational, private research or criticism and review purposes, which would make fanfiction *de jure* illegal. However, both these laws were drawn up before the advent of the World Wide Web made fanfiction such a widespread phenomenon. Since both the American and British legal systems are precedent-based it would require a test case for the situation to be clarified, a test case which could draw on a number of legal arguments, including the fair use, parody and implied consent defences.

²⁵ Granick, Jennifer. Harry Potter Loves Malfoy, *Wired Magazine* [online]. <<http://www.wired.com/politics/law/commentary/circuitcourt/2006/08/71597>>, [16.08.06], [accessed 15.06.07].

²⁶ Leonard, Sean. Celebrating Two Decades of Unlawful Progress: Fan Distribution, Proselytization Commons, and the Explosive Growth of Japanese Animation, *UCLA Entertainment Law Review* [online], 2005, 12(2). <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=696402>, [accessed 15.06.07]

Unfortunately, no such case has ever been brought. Consequently, there is simply no case law concerning fanfiction in particular and widespread, non-profit, fan-based perceived copyright infringement of characters in general. As a result of this legal uncertainty, fanfiction currently exists in a grey area where it is neither legal nor illegal – one side perceives it to be illegal and acts accordingly and the other side feels that it is *not* illegal and carries on with its activities, occasionally bowing to legal intimidation as expediency requires. In essence, fanfiction is the classic legal Schrödinger’s cat scenario: it is neither legal nor illegal and will remain at this legal impasse until a judge or law-maker opens the box and looks at the issue.

A major part of this conflict between fans and ‘The Powers That Be’ is the idea of perceptions of ownership. Whilst fans would never deny that the characters they use in their fanfiction belong legally to the authors or media corporations, they do feel a certain amount of emotional ownership over the characters. As Sheenagh Pugh writes in *The Democratic Genre*, her study of fanfiction in a literary context, “[fanfic writers] do speak and think of ‘our characters’, a shared resource that the whole community of that fandom feels it know and cares about.”²⁷

Deborah Halbert argues that the current copyright system is rooted in 18th-century notions of proprietary ownership best suited to the print/analog age and is resistant to change because that would involve a certain amount of authorial loss of control. She writes:

“The copyright system has helped create a unified notion of authorship and creativity that can help enforce the boundaries of ownership and is currently being used to further expand and cement ownership. Copyright turns the author into a conceptually coherent subject when the reality is the opposite. People working as authors, readers, professors, and creators are multiple and diverse, their reasons for creating are many, and the way they share, appropriate, and own information varied...when technology makes it

²⁷ Pugh, Sheenagh. *The Democratic Genre*, 2005, p. 67.

possible to exchange, collaborate, borrow, and steal like never before, the notion of authorship inevitably changes. Copyright, however, continues to force the dialogue into that occupied by the individual authorial subject who is protected by a system of rights.”²⁸

Fanfiction is part of a sea-change in attitude that is starting to change the way the copyright system views ownership, recognising that, as Halbert writes, “the overemphasis of ownership is the logical outcome of the existing law that assumes the author is a coherent identity, that the text never changes, and that ownership is the best method for facilitating creativity”²⁹ and that the “proprietary framework that has dominated intellectual property law has not been capable of dealing with the new relationships between the author, the reader, and the text that emerge with the introduction of computer technology.”³⁰ More than anything else, fanfiction defines this idea of a new relationship between author, reader and text, wherein readers become writers, writers become readers and the text is fluid and changing between the two.

2.2 Copyright Law

Under US copyright law, embodied in Section 106 of the 1976 Copyright Act, authors and creators are granted the exclusive right to “prepare derivative works based upon the copyrighted work”³¹. UK copyright law, embodied by the 1988 Copyrights, Designs and Patents Act, whilst not using the term ‘derivative works’, does grant the exclusive right to “to make an adaptation of the work or do any of the above [i.e. copy, issue copies, perform or broadcast] in relation to an adaptation”³². UK law also grants the author a moral right to object to derogatory treatment of his/her work³³.

²⁸ Halbert, Deborah. *Intellectual Property in the Information Age*, 1999, p. 141-142.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 122.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 121.

³¹ United States, 1976. Copyright Act 1976. <<http://www.copyright.gov/title17/circ92.pdf>>, [accessed 12.07.07]

³² Great Britain, 1988. Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988. <http://www.opsi.gov.uk/acts/acts1988/Ukpga_19880048_en_1.htm>, [accessed 12.07.07]

³³ *Ibid.*

In addition, both the US and UK are signatories to the World Trade Organization Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), an international agreement that sets down minimum standards for many forms of intellectual property. Under TRIPS, which in many places incorporates whole sections of the Berne Convention, authors “enjoy the exclusive right of authorizing adaptations, arrangements and other alterations of their works.”³⁴

Both UK and US laws contain, respectively, ‘fair dealing’ and ‘fair use’ exceptions, which allow for use of copyrighted material without permission in a number of specific circumstances, which include research or private study, criticism or review, incidental inclusion in an artistic work and use for purposes of instruction or examination. There is no specific exception for fanfiction or anything of its kind, and since we have already defined fanfiction as a derivative work, the right to which is solely reserved by the author or copyright holder, it would seem clear then that fanfiction is *de jure* illegal.

However, copyright law does recognise the importance of not allowing restrictive laws to stifle creativity. As Judge O’Connor wrote in *Feist Publications Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Co.*, “The primary objective of copyright is not to reward the labor of authors, but to promote the progress of science and the arts. To this end, copyright assures authors the right to their original expression but encourages others to build freely upon the ideas and information conveyed by a work.”³⁵

2.2.1 Fair Use

The American ‘fair use’ doctrine is much more flexible than its British equivalent, containing a provision for four factors which can be used in

³⁴ Great Britain, 1994. Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS). <http://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/analytic_index_e/trips_04_e.htm>, [accessed 12.07.07]

³⁵ *Feist Publications, Inc., v. Rural Telephone Service Co.*, 499 U.S. 340 [1991]

determining whether or not a particular use of copyrighted material not specifically mentioned is a fair use:

- “(1) the purpose and character of the use, including whether such use is of a commercial nature or is for nonprofit educational purposes;
- (2) the nature of the copyrighted work;
- (3) the amount and substantiality of the portion used in relation to the copyrighted work as a whole; and
- (4) the effect of the use upon the potential market for or value of the copyrighted work”³⁶

The question then is to determine whether and to what extent these four factors can be applied to fanfiction in order to justify its inclusion in a fair use exception.

As mentioned previously, fanfiction is a non-profit, creative activity perpetrated by fans as an expression of love and affection for the original material. These fans have no desire to harm or distort the original material – indeed, in most cases they are the prime paying market for it. Fanfiction is generally created as a result of personal creative impulses and not as a means to fame or financial benefit. There are arguably a number of educational benefits to be reaped from fanfiction – in a survey of fanfiction writers conducted for the purposes of this dissertation, 87% of respondents believed that the reading and writing of fanfiction had a beneficial effect on their own literacy. This would certainly seem to satisfy most of the conditions of Factor 1.

One of the most important additional aspects of Factor 1 is the so-called ‘transformative’ argument, originally developed in *Campbell v. Acuff-Rose Music, Inc.*, wherein a derivative work is found to add “something new, with a further purpose or different character, altering the first with new expression, meaning or message”³⁷. In the recent case *Blanch v. Koons* (2006), the US Court

³⁶ United States, 1976. Copyright Act 1976. <<http://www.copyright.gov/title17/circ92.pdf>>, [accessed 12.07.07]

³⁷ *Campbell v. Acuff-Rose Music*, 510 U.S. 569 [1994]

of Appeals of the Second Circuit stated that the courts will not “find a transformative use when the defendant has done no more than find a new way to exploit the creative virtues of the original work”³⁸. The Chilling Effects Clearinghouse, a joint project between the Electronic Frontier Foundation and a number of American law schools, including those of Harvard and Stanford, argues that many fanfiction stories are transformative “since they create a different persona and set of events for the character”³⁹.

Factor 2 is arguably one of the most problematic for fanfiction. ‘The nature of the copyrighted work’ refers to the style and content of the copyrighted work in question; in the case of fanfiction this would be published fictional material, both in print and onscreen. As current copyright law is designed to promote originality, imaginative fictional works are much less likely to be subject to fair use than factual works. However, as Anthony Falzone, executive director of the Fair Use Project at Stanford University, has argued, Factor 2 tends to be the least important of the fair use factors and the distinction between factual and fictional would be unlikely to tip the balance one way or the other⁴⁰. There is also a much stronger case for fair use with published works, since an author has made the decision to release his creation into the public domain.

Factor 3, the amount and substantiality of the copyrighted work used, is somewhat difficult to define in terms of fanfiction. In terms of tangible material, i.e. the actual text of a book or the script of a film or television program, fanfiction takes almost nothing. It is very rare to find any verbatim sections of text or script used in a fanfiction story. However, in terms of the intangible material, i.e. the characters or the fictional universe, fanfiction takes almost everything. Indeed, it would be almost impossible to write a fanfiction story based on *Harry Potter*, for example, without drawing on the world of *Harry Potter* in its entirety, unless the story in question was an AU (alternative

³⁸ *Blanch v. Koons*, 467 F.3d 244 [2006]

³⁹ Chilling Effects Clearinghouse.

<<http://www.chillingeffects.org/question.cgi?QuestionID=138>>, [n.d.], [accessed 07.06.07]

⁴⁰ Falzone, Anthony. Interview, *Pro & Content* [online], 2007, 8,

<[http://www.imakenews.com/proandcontent/e_article000781406.cfm?x=b11,0,w](http://www.imakenews.com/proandcontent/e_article000781406.cfm?x=b11,0,w>)>, [accessed 27.07.07]

universe), wherein the characters are taken out of their original context and set within a different world: Harry Potter in the American Civil War, for example.

There is also the matter of whether characters (as opposed to characters' names, which would of course be covered by separate trademark law) can even be copyrighted, which is not clear under US law. UK law is somewhat simpler – characters cannot be copyrighted. As Nicola Solomon writes, “copyright protects the words and form in which ideas are expressed, not the ideas or characters themselves.”⁴¹

Under US copyright law there are two ‘tests’ which have been used to determine whether or not to afford copyright protection to characters – the ‘character delineation’ test and the ‘story being told’ test⁴². The former, developed by Justice Hand in *Nichols v. Universal Pictures Corp (1930)*, requires that a character needs to be sufficiently delineated and developed in order to be afforded copyright protection⁴³. A stock or archetypal character would not be distinctive enough to be afforded protection. The second test was introduced in *Warner Brothers v. Columbia Broadcasting Systems (1954)*, which stated that the character, in this case Sam Spade of *The Maltese Falcon*, could not be copyrighted because “if the character is only the chessman in the game of telling the story he is not within the area of the protection afforded by copyright.”⁴⁴ Unfortunately, these tests are not always applied consistently – when Rocky Balboa is afforded copyright protection⁴⁵ but Sam Spade is not, it is hard to judge which way the ruling may fall next time a similar case comes up.

The final factor used in determining fair use, the effect of the use on the market value of the original material, is, as the Supreme Court stated in *Harper & Row v. Nation Enterprises*, “undoubtedly the single most important element of fair

⁴¹ Solomon, Nicola. What A Character: Protecting and Exploiting Rights in Characters, *The Author* [online], Spring '01. <<http://www.akme.btinternet.co.uk/solomn14.html>>, [accessed 05.06.07]

⁴² Zecevic, Jasmina. Distinctly delineated fictional characters, *Vanderbilt Journal of Entertainment and Tech Law*, 2006, 8(2), p.365-397.

⁴³ *Nichols v. Universal Pictures Corporation*, 45 F.2d 119 [2d Cir. 1930]

⁴⁴ *Warner Brothers v. Columbia Broadcasting Systems*, 216 F.2d 945 [9th Cir. 1954]

⁴⁵ *Anderson v. Stallone*, 11 USPQ2D 1161 [C.D. Cal. 1989]

use⁴⁶ and often one of the most complex. The non-commercial, fan-based nature of fanfiction makes this somewhat simpler, for the very reason that the market for fanfiction and the original copyrighted product is one and the same. This might suggest that fanfiction would be in direct competition with the original copyrighted product, albeit not in financial terms, but this is not the case. Fans read fanfiction because they are fans of the original material and want more than is available on the market. If an individual is enough of a fan of *Star Wars* to be reading *Star Wars* fanfiction, he or she is unlikely to then reject the official product that is the root of his/her passion purely in favour of an unofficial, fan-created product. Indeed, in the survey of fanfiction writers undertaken for this dissertation, 63% of respondents had purchased official tie-in novels in the past, despite 79% of that number rating the standard as poor or average.

There are also several issues that affect the determining of fair use that do not fall under the four factors listed above. For example, disclaimers are used by almost all fanfiction writers to highlight the unofficial nature of the story in question and to acknowledge the source material drawn upon. In and of itself, a disclaimer is not protection against legal action, but in a particularly close case where the court may find one way or the other, a disclaimer can often have a significant effect on the way the court views the use.

The finding of fair use is often a highly subjective issue and, although it has no basis in law, an individual judge's own sense of right and wrong or moral standards can have an effect. Explicitly pornographic fanfiction featuring the under-age characters of J.K. Rowling's *Harry Potter* series, for example, or incestuous fanfiction featuring the Winchester brothers from the CW's *Supernatural* television series may be eyed askance by a particularly moral judge.

⁴⁶ *Harper & Row v. Nation Enterprises*, 471 U.S. 539 [1985]

2.2.2 Parodies

Neither US nor UK law contains a specific fair use exception for parodies, although the 2006 Gowers Review, an independent review of intellectual property rights commissioned by HM Government, has recommended that an amendment be made to UK law to allow for this⁴⁷. Both countries' copyright laws do include a fair use exception for the purposes of criticism and commentary, and it is this exception that is used as a defence on behalf of parodies.

Under US law, there have two particular rulings on parodies that could have an effect on fanfiction. In *Acuff-Rose Music Inc v Campbell*, Judge Nelson defined a parody as “a work that transforms all or a significant part of an original work of authorship into a derivative work by distorting it or closely imitating it, for comic [...] effect, in a manner such that both the original work of authorship and the independent effort of the parodist are recognizable.”⁴⁸ The key word in this definition would seem to be ‘comic’, requiring that a derivative or transformative work must have a humorous intent in order to be protected as a parody. The vast majority of fanfiction, whilst conforming to every other aspect of this definition, is not humorous in tone. This would tend to suggest that fanfiction would not benefit from parodic protection, as it lacks this vital ingredient.

This comedic definition of parody, however, is not used consistently. In *Suntrust v. Houghton Mifflin Co.*, the novel *The Wind Done Gone*, a parallel novel to Margaret Mitchell's *Gone with the Wind* portraying the point-of-view of the slaves on Scarlett O'Hara's cotton plantation, was permitted publication by the US Court of Appeals for the Eleventh Circuit, and is indeed published with the disclaimer ‘the unofficial parody’, despite not being humorous in tone or intent. The Court found that *The Wind Done Gone* was “critical by constitution, its main aim being to shatter *Gone With the Wind*'s window on life in the antebellum and Civil War South” and that the author, Alice Randall, “radically reshapes what she borrows from Mitchell”; before going on to define a work as a parody “if its

⁴⁷ Gowers, Andrew. *Gowers Review of Intellectual Property*, 2006, p. 6

⁴⁸ *Acuff-Rose Music Inc v Campbell*, 972 F.2d 1429 [6th Cir. 1992]

aim is to comment upon or criticize a prior work by appropriating elements of the original in creating a new artistic [...] work.” The Court also added that:

“Had Randall chosen to write *The Wind Done Gone* from the point of view of one of Mitchell’s original characters, for example, and done no more than put a new gloss on the familiar tale without criticizing or commenting on its fundamental theme and spirit, Houghton Mifflin’s case would have been much tougher.”⁴⁹

Whilst as first glance this lack of requirement for a humorous or comedic tone would seem to support fanfiction’s case, in actual fact it further undermines it by requiring that a parody ‘comment upon or criticize’ the original work whose elements it is appropriating. Again, whilst some fanfiction may fulfill this requirement, the overwhelming majority does not; indeed, a great deal of fanfiction conforms exactly to what the Court warned against: retelling the story from a different point-of-view without any fundamental criticism or commentary. A comparable situation can be found in the previously mentioned *Rogers v Koons*, where the Court found that a sculpture created by the defendant did not merit parodic protection since it copied many elements of the original but did not specifically target or comment upon it⁵⁰.

It seems clear that under US law at least, fanfiction would not be able to derive any kind of copyright protection from arguing for its inclusion under the commentary/criticism exception as a parody, although whether it would do so under UK law is another matter.

In UK case law two tests have evolved that are used to judge the merits of a parody held to have infringed copyright. The first, the ‘substantial part test’, was developed by Judge Falconer in *Schweppes Ltd and Others v Wellingtons Ltd* in 1984, wherein a defendant must prove that there has been no reproduction of a substantial part of the original work, a difficult task for a parody that relies on

⁴⁹ *Suntrust v. Houghton Mifflin Co.*, 252 F. 3d 1165 [11th Cir. 2001] *per curiam*, opinion at 268 F.3d 1257

⁵⁰ *Rogers v. Koons*, 960 F.2d 301 [2d Cir. 1992]

use of a substantial amount of the original copyrighted work in order to be understood by its target audience⁵¹. This raises a problem already explored in the section on the four Fair Use factors of US copyright – does ‘a substantial part’ relate to verbatim copying of the original text or does it refer to more intangible material such as the fictional world and the characters? Unfortunately, there has as yet been no clarification of this complex issue in either country’s legal system, so the question of whether fanfiction’s use of said world and characters would constitute a substantial part of the original material is still unclear.

The second test, the ‘mental labour test’, was originally developed by Judge Younger in *Glyn v Weston Feature Film Company* and enhanced by Judge McNair in *Joy Music Ltd v Sunday Pictorial Newspapers (1920) Ltd*. This test requires that a defendant demonstrate that he/she has “bestowed such mental labour on what he [has] taken and subjected it to such revision and alteration as to produce an original work.”⁵² This test is similar to the ‘transformative’ argument used under Factor 1 of the US Fair Use test, wherein a derivative work must demonstrate that it adds something new to the original material to make it a new work in its own right. As we have already seen, many law experts agree that fanfiction does conform to this requirement.

The requirements for protection as a parody under both US and UK law often seem conflicting or contradictory, largely because there is no specific legislation on this issue. For example, one ruling makes it clear that a parody must have a comedic tone, and yet another ruling suggests this is not necessary. One ruling requires that a parody must transform the original material sufficiently to make a creation that is new and transformative, yet in order to be understood by its target audience a parody must closely imitate or mimic the original, which it cannot do if it is not permitted to use a substantial part of the original material. As long as this confusing state of affairs remain in place, it would be difficult for fanfiction to base a sound legal argument on the parody principle.

⁵¹ *Schweppes Ltd and Others v Wellingtons Ltd.*, FSR 210 [1984]

⁵² *Glyn v Weston Feature Film Company*, 1 Ch. 261[1910]

2.2.3 Implied Consent

The common law doctrine of ‘implied consent’, as Meredith McCardle argues, “may be the strongest argument a fan fiction author can make”⁵³, albeit only in certain specific situations. The argument can be used in circumstances where an author or copyright holder is aware of the existence of fanfiction and has made no objections or indeed even encouraged it to continue. So for example, in the case of fanfiction based upon Terry Pratchett’s *Discworld* series, the author’s statement that “I don't actually object to fan fiction...provided that it's put somewhere where I don't trip over it...isn't done for money, and isn't passed off as 'official' in any way”⁵⁴ could be interpreted as implied consent. Having made this statement and thereby implied consent, Terry Pratchett could find it difficult to bring a suit against a fan story based upon his works, as long as the story in question did not violate the conditions laid out in his statement.

The principle of implied consent tends to be more applicable to fanfiction based on books than films or television programs, largely because in the case of the former the author/creator and copyright holder are more often than not one and the same person. In the case of a television program - *Buffy the Vampire Slayer*, for example - Joss Whedon is the creator and writer and as such garners most of the press attention that leads to such statements, but he does not own the copyright to his creation, which is held by Warner Bros. Joss Whedon is aware of the existence of fanfiction and has often made statements encouraging it, but his words would not imply consent since the consent is not his to give.

Columnist Cathy Young has even argued that such statements of implied consent may not even be necessary, that “in the absence of such explicit statements,

⁵³ McCardle, Meredith. Fandom, Fan Fiction, and Fanfare: What's All the Fuss?, *Boston University Journal of Science and Technology Law* [online], 2003, 9(2). <<http://www.bu.edu/law/central/jd/organizations/journals/scitech/volume92/mccardle.pdf>>, [accessed 03.05.07]

⁵⁴ Pratchett, Terry. *alt.books.pratchett* mailing list. <<http://faqs.cs.uu.nl/nabng/alt.books.pratchett.html>>, [23 Jan 1999], [accessed 17.06.07]

given that the widespread existence of fan fiction is by now no secret to anyone, I think silence may be presumed to equal consent”⁵⁵

2.2.4 De Minimis

The Latin expression *de minimis* comes from the phrase *de minimis non curat lex* and roughly translates as ‘the law does not concern itself about trifles’. It essentially means that although technically a law may have been violated, the actual infringement is so trivial that the court may ignore it altogether.

In the US, courts have applied the de minimis defence in three particular ways: when the “technical violation of a right [is] so trivial that the law will not impose legal consequences”⁵⁶, which has become synonymous with the idea of insignificant economic damage; when “copying has occurred to such a trivial extent as to fall below the quantitative threshold of substantial similarity”⁵⁷; and when it is “considered relevant to the defense of fair use”⁵⁸. It is highly likely that fanfiction, being non-commercial, would satisfy the first of these conditions. Certainly it is difficult to see how much damage one individual writer’s amateur *Harry Potter* fanfiction could do to a global brand worth over \$4 billion⁵⁹. As we have seen, there are also valid fair use arguments that would satisfy the third condition.

The second of the three conditions, that of substantial similarity, raises many of the same uncertainties highlighted under the second of the four fair use factors, “the amount and substantiality of the portion used”⁶⁰. As we have seen, fanfiction very rarely incorporates verbatim segments of text or script, but it does

⁵⁵ Young, Cathy. Lee Goldberg’s war on fanfic, *Reason Magazine* [online], 07.02.07. <<http://www.reason.com/blog/show/118582.html>>, [accessed 01.07.07]

⁵⁶ *Ringgold v. Black Entertainment Television*, 126 F.3d 70, 74 [2d Cir. 1997]

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ Brown, Stephen. Harry Potter Brand Magic, *Business Week* [online], 18 July 2005. <http://www.businessweek.com/innovate/content/jul2005/di20050721_060250.htm>, [accessed 09.06.07]

⁶⁰ United States, 1976. Copyright Act 1976. <<http://www.copyright.gov/title17/circ92.pdf>>, [accessed 12.07.07]

draw upon the work as a whole for inspiration. It may be argued, using *Harper & Row v. Nation Enterprises* as a guide, that although the amount of material borrowed is insubstantial, what has been taken, most particularly the characters, is the “heart of the book”⁶¹. Unfortunately, this gives rise to the same uncertainty as to whether characters can indeed be copyrighted, which, as we have seen, is not at all clear.

De minimis cannot be used as an argument for legality on behalf of fanfiction in general, but it can be used on an individual basis and may go some way to explaining why it may take a long time for fanfiction’s legal position to be defined. The court would have to judge each case on its own merits and not as part of a larger context; therefore, whilst fanfiction in general may be a considerable copyright dilemma for corporations, each individual writer’s output could be considered *de minimis* and therefore permitted under law.

Under UK law the *de minimis* principle is only taken into account by courts when awarding costs. In a case involving fanfiction any damages awarded against the defendant by a court - if indeed damages were awarded at all, bearing in mind the non-commercial nature of fanfiction – may well not be enough to outweigh the costs of pursuing the case. There may thus be no financial incentive for the copyright holder(s) to bring a suit against an individual fanfiction writer or fanzine.

This lack of financial punitive damages would mean that the sole reason for pursuing fanfiction through the courts would be to establish a legal precedent. At present, neither side particularly wishes to see this happen, since there is no guarantee as to which way the ruling would go, and both sides have much to lose, the corporate copyright holders most of all. As a result, so far any case that has progressed further than the issuing of a C&D letter has been settled out of court, generally to the advantage of the fanfiction writers.

⁶¹ *Harper & Row v. Nation Enterprises*, 471 U.S. 539 [1985]

Chapter 3

‘The Powers That Be’

3.1 Attitudes & Opinions

There is very little consensus on the issue of fanfiction amongst authors, creators and other such copyright holders. Many are wholly in favour of fanfiction, in theory at least; others are firmly against it for a variety of reasons that will be explored later, some legal or financial, some emotional. There is also an interesting, although perhaps not surprising, difference between the reactions of copyright holders who have a more immediate, personal connection with the material, such as authors of novels, and those whose connection is somewhat more distant or diluted, such as film and television scriptwriters and producers.

Writing a novel is very much a solitary pursuit, at least until the editing and publication stages: as such, it is no wonder that many authors refer to their work as ‘their baby’ and as Carol Pinchefsky has written, “for some authors, creation means ownership.”⁶² Writing for film and television, however, is often very much a collaborative process with any number of writers involved. William Bielby has argued that this collaborative or group writing process and the “legal and organizational arrangements [that] deny legitimacy to the ‘true’ authors ... [have contributed] to a sense that ownership of the narratives can be contested”⁶³. It is also this situation which lends distance from the material to its creators, a distance which allows them to view fanfiction writers’ actions with more tolerance and leniency than an individual author might.

⁶² Carol Pinchefsky, Fan Fiction and Contradiction, *InterGalactic Medicine Show* [online], 2007, 5. <http://www.intergalacticmedicineshow.com/cgi-bin/mag.cgi?do=columns&vol=carol_pinchefsky&article=008>, [accessed 13.05.07]

⁶³ Bielby, William. Whose Stories Are They? Fans’ Engagement with Soap Opera Narratives in Three Sites of Fan Activity. *Journal of Broadcasting and Electronic Media* [online], 1999, 43(1). <<http://www.allbusiness.com/information/internet-publishing-broadcasting/164684-2.html>>, [accessed 05.06.07]

3.1.1 In Print

As mentioned above, some authors' negative reactions to fanfiction can be intensely personal. For example, in April 2000 Anne Rice, one of the most well-known of the anti-fanfiction authors, posted a message on her website stating, "I do not allow fan fiction. ... It upsets me terribly to even think about fan fiction with my characters. I advise my readers to write your own original stories with your own characters. It is absolutely essential that you respect my wishes."⁶⁴

In a similar vein, Ursula K. LeGuin has described fanfiction as "an invasion, literally — strangers coming in and taking over the country I live in, my heartland"⁶⁵ and Yasmin Galenorn has written that,

"Emotionally, it's like having somebody else shove their way into my characters [sic] lives and my worlds. These characters are very much like my children. How would you like someone writing slash fiction about your kids, or someone you love and live with on a daily basis?"⁶⁶

Other writers dislike being associated against their will with material they have no control over: Robin Hobb, a fantasy novelist, has said,

"Suppose you did a Google search for your own name, and found that someone had written an article condemning the civil rights movement, and used quotes from your work out of context, and attached your name as an authority for it. Or if someone put up a Wikipedia article about you that listed a substantial criminal history that wasn't yours. You might be horrified, yes? Fan fiction does that to established fiction writers. It links not just a quality

⁶⁴ Rice, Anne. *Anne Rice.com*. <<http://www.annerice.com/>>, [07.04.2000], [accessed 19.06.07]

⁶⁵ LeGuin, Ursula K. *Ursula K. LeGuin's Web Site*. <http://www.ursulakleguin.com/FAQ_Questionnaire5_01.html#FF>, [n.d.], [accessed 19.06.07]

⁶⁶ Galenorn, Yasmin. *The Teashop*. <<http://www.galenorn.com/teashop/index.php?body=ascopyright.htm>>, [n.d.], [accessed 19.06.07]

of text, but ideas to a writer's name, in a way that the writer cannot control.”⁶⁷

Some writers have financial concerns over fanfiction. Orson Scott Card has written that fanfiction is “an attack on my means of livelihood”⁶⁸, “the inheritance of my children”⁶⁹ and that he views fanfiction as akin to “moving into my house without invitation and throwing out my family”⁷⁰.

There are also legal concerns for the authors themselves, an aspect of fanfiction that is often overlooked. One of the most frequently recounted tales of an author’s run-in with fanfiction involves the science-fiction/fantasy author Marion Zimmer Bradley. Bradley ran a fanzine for her *Darkover* fantasy series, for which fans submitted stories. In 1992 Bradley was sued by a fan who had submitted a story for inclusion in this fanzine and then subsequently claimed that Bradley had stolen ideas from this story for her forthcoming novel *Contraband*. The fan demanded half the royalties from this book and also to be credited as co-author. Rather than face a lengthy lawsuit, Bradley’s publishers at the time, Daw Books, pulled *Contraband* from its publication schedule and the novel has never yet been published. Bradley also ceased production of the *Darkover* fanzine and stated that she would no longer tolerate fanfiction based on her works⁷¹.

Before this incident Marion Zimmer Bradley was a great proponent of fanfiction, as demonstrated by her willingness to run a fanzine for her *Darkover* series:

“I don't mind other writers writing about Darkover ... Nor do I feel threatened by stories not consistent with my personal vision of Darkover [...] If others wish to play in my fantasy world, who am I to slam its gates and in

⁶⁷ Hobb, Robin. Cited in Carol Pinchefskey, Fan Fiction and Contradiction, *InterGalatic Medicine Show* [online], 2007, 5. <http://www.intergalacticmedicineshow.com/cgi-bin/mag.cgi?do=columns&vol=carol_pinchefskey&article=008>, [accessed 13.05.07]

⁶⁸ Card, Orson Scott. *Questions For a Research Paper*. <<http://www.hatrack.com/research/interviews/yoda-patta.shtml>>, [1997], [accessed 19.06.07]

⁶⁹ Card, Orson Scott. *OSC Answers Questions*. <<http://www.hatrack.com/research/questions/q0121.shtml>>, [19.06.04], [accessed 19.06.07]

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*

⁷¹ Ecks, Michaela. Fan Fiction, Novels, Copyright and Ethics. *Whoosh* [online], 62, November 2001. <<http://www.whoosh.org/issue62/ecks2.html>>, [accessed 15.06.07]

churlish voice demand that they build their own? If they are capable of it, they will do so someday. Meanwhile, if they wish to write of Darkover, they will.”⁷²

The *Contraband* incident typifies one of the major concerns of many professional authors - that in encouraging fanfiction based on their work they are leaving themselves open to subsequent lawsuits. Mercedes Lackey, an award-winning fantasy novelist who began by writing *Darkover* fanfiction, has stated that as a result of the ‘MZB incident’, as it is known online, she no longer reads any fanfiction based upon her work, although she did add that “just because I don't read fan fiction doesn't mean you shouldn't write it if you want to”⁷³. She now requires that all fans submitting stories to official fanzines based on her material fill in a legal release form setting out the rights of both Lackey and the fans, in order to avoid a repeat of Bradley’s experience.

Lackey’s position is not unusual amongst authors. Many share her position – that fanfiction is permissible as long as it conforms to certain pre-conditions. J.K. Rowling, for instance, has stated that she has read some of the *Harry Potter* fanfiction online and finds it “very flattering that people love the characters that much”⁷⁴, but a spokesman for Rowling’s literary agent later added that “if young children were to stumble on Harry Potter in a an x-rated story, that would be a problem.”⁷⁵

The negative or hesitant positions of many of the aforementioned authors are however in the minority. A great many authors see no harm in fans writing fanfiction; others are wholly in favour of fanfiction; some freely confess to reading it and a few even write it themselves! Meg Cabot, for instance, used to

⁷² Bradley, Marion Zimmer. Cited in *Fan Works Inc.* <<http://www.fanworks.org/writersresource/?tool=fanpolicy&action=define&authorid=53>>, [n.d.], [accessed 17.07.07]

⁷³ Lackey, Mercedes. *Ask Misty Archive – Writing*. <http://www.mercedeslackey.com/am_writing.html>, [2003], [accessed 15.06.07]

⁷⁴ Rowling, J. K. *Live interview with Scholastic.com*. <<http://www.scholastic.com/harrypotter/books/author/interview2.htm>>, [16.10.00], [accessed 12.05.07]

⁷⁵ BBC News. Rowling backs Potter fan fiction. <<http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/entertainment/arts/3753001.stm>>, [27.05.05], [accessed 18.08.07]

write *Star Wars* fanfiction⁷⁶ and Mercedes Lackey has confessed to still writing fanfiction set in the role-playing game *City of Heroes*⁷⁷.

Referring back to the idea that an author's work is akin to 'their baby', Lackey goes on to say that,

"I have a kind of complicated relationship with my books. They are my babies right up until the point where they leave my hands. Then they become something else, and that something else is different to everyone who reads them. I can't control that. It's stupid to try. All I can really do is tell the best story I can, and what happens after that is out of my hands. The babies have grown up and become independent, and like a wise parent I do my best to let go."⁷⁸

This metaphor of 'books as babies' is echoed by Lois McMaster Bujold:

"I'm a control freak with respect to my own work up to the time the galley proofs leave my hand. At that point, I believe -- reluctantly -- that I have to cut the umbilicus and let the work sink or swim as best it can."⁷⁹

Bestselling author Naomi Novik, writer of the historical-fantasy *Temeraire* series, has written effusively in her blog about her appreciation for and approval of fanfiction:

"I for one would be thrilled to know that people loved my characters and my world enough to want to come on in and play, not to mention that I would be wildly grateful for the free publicity. ... If they did, that would mean I was doing something fundamentally right -- that I was creating characters that

⁷⁶ Cabot, Meg. *Meg's Diary*. <<http://www.megcabot.com/diary/?p=158>>, [12.05.05], [accessed 06.06.07]

⁷⁷ Lackey, Mercedes. *Making Light*. <<http://nielsenhayden.com/makinglight/archives/007464.html#122221>>, [26.04.06], [accessed 06.06.07]

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

⁷⁹ Bujold, Lois McMaster. Cited in Carol Pinchefsky, Fan Fiction and Contradiction, *InterGalactic Medicine Show* [online], 2007, 5. <http://www.intergalacticmedicineshow.com/cgi-bin/mag.cgi?do=columns&vol=carol_pinchefsky&article=008>, [accessed 13.05.07]

people wanted to make part of the shared culture by which we communicate with one another. ... Not only would I not look down upon that kind of fannish activity, I would love to do whatever I can to encourage it.”⁸⁰

3.1.2 Onscreen

There is an interesting dichotomy in the world of film and television, in that very often the individuals who create and write the material used by fans in their fanfiction are not the copyright holders. These individuals are generally the ones who garner the press attention and make statements concerning fanfiction, yet their words carry no official weight and one cannot always assume that they are speaking for the corporations behind them. It is these major media corporations who hold the power of copyright, yet they are generally silent on the issue, except when they take action against fanfiction.

Many writers view the existence of fanfiction based upon their television shows or films as a great compliment, proof of the existence of a hardcore base of loyal fans, a valuable commodity in the modern television industry. As Ronald D. Moore, writer and producer of numerous shows, including *Star Trek*, *Roswell* and *Battlestar Galactica*, has said,

“I think it’s great. I think it’s an expression of people’s love and affection for a show. The fact that people would take the time to sit down and write entire storylines, wrapped around back story and characters that are established, do elaborate plots and write serials, it’s a remarkable tribute to the appeal of those shows.”⁸¹

⁸⁰ Novik, Naomi. *A Few More Times Around on the Little Wheel*.

<<http://naominovik.livejournal.com/17128.html>>, [16.06.05], [accessed 03.06.07]

⁸¹ Ronald D. Moore. Cited in Arpe, Marlene. Television’s afterlife. *Toronto Star* [online], 22nd May 2004.

<<http://pqasb.pqarchiver.com/thestar/offers.html?url=%2Fthestar%2Faccess%2F640138751.html%3Fdids%3D640138751%3A640138751%26FMT%3DFT%26FMTS%3DABS%3AFT%26date%3DMay%2B22%252C%2B2004%26author%3DMalene%2BArpe%26pub%3DToronto%2BStar%26edition%3D%26startpage%3DJ.01%26desc%3DTelevision%2527s%2Bafterlife%26>>, [accessed 03.05.07]

This sentiment of Moore's is reiterated by a number of film and television writers, including Joss Whedon, creator, writer, director and executive producer of *Firefly*, *Buffy the Vampire Slayer* and its spin-off *Angel* and a great favourite of fans:

"I love it. I absolutely love it. I wish I had grown up in the era of fan fiction ... I think it's kind of a glorious thing to be able to be carrying the torch. That's why I made these shows. I didn't make them so that people would enjoy them and forget them; I made them so they would never be able to shake them. It's the way I am as a fan. I create the shows that would make me do that."⁸²

Many actors whose characters appear in fanfiction are likewise as open-minded: Scott Cohen, star of *The 10th Kingdom*, wrote in a letter to fans that he was "flattered and grateful for this outpouring of support, admiration and recognition. I am moved to tears actually at how my performance has moved so many others. The websites are magnificent. All the photos, artwork, chats, fiction and videos are really great."⁸³ Jason Isaacs, who plays Lucius Malfoy in the *Harry Potter* films, has confessed to reading fanfiction involving Malfoy and getting "a huge kick out of the more far-out stuff."⁸⁴

Abiding by J.K. Rowling's example, Warner Brothers, which owns the film rights to the *Harry Potter* series, has been generally forbearing of fanfiction, although it has been known to crack down on adult or pornographic fanfiction. Fanfiction is permitted as long it abides by the terms and conditions laid out by the corporation. This is a similar position to that of Lucasfilm, which does not permit any kind of explicit or pornographic fanfiction based on *Star Wars*:

⁸² Whedon, Joss. Cited in Arpe, Marlene. Television's afterlife. *Toronto Star* [online], 22nd May 2004.

<<http://pqasb.pqarchiver.com/thestar/offers.html?url=%2Fthestar%2Faccess%2F640138751.html%3Fdids%3D640138751%3A640138751%26FMT%3DFT%26FMTS%3DABS%3AFT%26date%3DMay%2B22%252C%2B2004%26author%3DMalene%2BArpe%26pub%3DToronto%2BStar%26edition%3D%26startpage%3DJ.01%26desc%3DTelevision%2527s%2BAfterlife>>, [accessed 03.05.07]

⁸³ Cohen, Scott. *Letter from Scott Cohen*. <<http://www.wolfpackclub.8m.com/letter.html>>, [n.d.], [accessed 24.06.07]

⁸⁴ Isaacs, Jason. *The Lexicon Visits the Magic Factory*. <<http://www.hp-lexicon.org/about/films/lex-op-set-teaser.html>>, [n.d.], [accessed 12.07.07]

“Since all of the Star Wars saga is PG-rated, any story those publishers [i.e. fanzines] print should also be PG. Lucasfilm does not produce any X-rated Star Wars episodes, so why should we be placed in a light where people think we do?”⁸⁵

Although this may seem a fairly straight-forward position, Lucasfilm has in fact one of the more ambiguous stances on fanfiction, sometimes appearing to condone it, at other times to condemn. For instance, the Vice-President of Marketing for Lucasfilm has stated, “If in fact someone is using our characters to create a story unto itself, that’s not in the spirit of what we think fandom is about. Fandom is about celebrating the story the way it is.”⁸⁶ Yet George Lucas himself has stated that he doesn’t care about fan fiction and that the fans can “write all the stories about Star Wars [they] so desire”⁸⁷ and the official *Star Wars* fan site, fan.starwars.com, provides webspace for fans to post their fanfiction as long as it remains for personal, non-commercial purposes.

Lucasfilm’s often contradictory stance towards fanfiction is indicative of a general problem for corporations in particular: they simply do not know what approach to take, torn between what Jenkins has called the collaborationist and the prohibitionist approaches⁸⁸. The corporations believe it necessary to assert their intellectual property rights over the material in order to protect their commercial interests, yet at the same time, as Jeanne Cole, a spokesman for Lucasfilm, has said, “What can you do? How can you control it? As we look at it, we appreciate the fans, and what would we do without them? If we anger them, what’s the point?”⁸⁹

⁸⁵ Cited in Jenkins, Henry. *Convergence Culture*, 2006, p.150

⁸⁶ Ward, Jim. Cited in Murray, Simone. Celebrating the Story the Way It Is: Cultural Studies, Corporate Media and the Contested Utility of Fandom. *Continuum: Journal of Media and Cultural Studies*, 2004, 18.1, p. 11

⁸⁷ Lucas, George. *The George Lucas Interviews at Supershadow*.
<<http://www.supershadow.com/starwars/lucas/>>, [n.d.], [accessed 04.05.07]

⁸⁸ Jenkins, Henry. *Convergence Culture*, 2006, p. 134

⁸⁹ Cited in *ibid.*, p. 142-143

Mark Justman has described this dilemma as “the front line in the battle between the conventional economy and the attention economy”⁹⁰. Cracking down on fan activities can make commercial sense: the fans are using copyrighted material; the product of their creative endeavours could conceivably draw attention away from official products and dilute the official image of characters that are worth millions in marketing terms. Yet at the same time these fans are often the most devoted and lucrative market available and provide a valuable source of free publicity and can often mean the difference between success and failure in the ruthless world of the media industry.

Harold Feld, a lawyer and Senior Vice-President of the Media Access Project, has warned that that,

“if the big media companies alienate the fans, the fans stop buying your comic books, stop going to your movies and stop watching your TV shows. Companies that hold the copyrights learn after a while that coming down with a sledgehammer is not the way to deal with [fan fiction].”⁹¹

3.2 Legal Action

Unfortunately, ‘coming down with a sledgehammer’ is exactly what some copyright holders have done, particularly individual authors who, in many cases, do not have the financial luxury that corporate owners do in taking a longer-term commercial viewpoint; and, as we have seen, are inclined to react more emotionally to begin with. One novelist, Holly Lisle, has promised to ‘prosecute’ any fans writing fanfiction based on her works⁹², unfortunately a somewhat uninformed statement since, as alleged copyright infringement, fanfiction would

⁹⁰ Justman, Mark. *Grassroots Fan Culture and Textual Poaching*. <<http://www.fortunecity.com/victorian/barchester/1341/poaching.htm>>, [20.03.00], [accessed 07.04.07]

⁹¹ Feld, Harold. Cited in Carol Pinchefskey, Fan Fiction and Contradiction, *InterGalactic Medicine Show* [online], 2007, 5. <http://www.intergalacticmedicineshow.com/cgi-bin/mag.cgi?do=columns&vol=carol_pinchefskey&article=008>, [accessed 13.05.07]

⁹² Lisle, Holly. *HollyLisle.com*. <<http://hollylisle.com/writingdiary/article.php/20050615150820744>>, [16.06.05], [accessed 29.06.07]

fall under civil and not criminal law. Fanfiction writers cannot therefore be prosecuted for their actions, but they can be sued.

As yet no fan has ever been sued for writing fanfiction. Some have received cease-and-desist letters demanding that the offending material be removed from the internet and in almost all cases the fans in question have complied with these demands. Some fans have however successfully fought back, particularly when the C&D letters have been issued on behalf of a large corporation, particularly within the *Harry Potter* fandom, as will be explored later. Corporate owners tend to adopt a policy of “benign neglect”⁹³, although every now and then they will crack down on fan activity, as though to remind fans that whilst the corporation tolerates fan activities they do still hold the power of copyright over them..

Many fan sites containing fanfiction have been shut down not as a result of the fanfiction itself but because of the additional inclusion of other copyrighted material, such as images, episode transcripts and video clips. In the mid 1990s 20th Century Fox in particular was quite zealous in shutting down *Buffy the Vampire Slayer* and *The X-Files* fan sites. Viacom, now know as CBS and owners of *Star Trek*, also shut down a number of *Star Trek* fan sites for similar offences. Only four of the sample C&D letters listed on Chilling Effects pertain exclusively to fanfiction.

Threats of legal action specifically against fanfiction can generally be broken in two particular types: when the copyright holder is set against fanfiction on principle and when the fanfiction in question has violated the generally accepted ‘rules of engagement’ laid down by the copyright holders: that fanfiction must remained non-commercial, must clearly state that it is a derivative unofficial work based on a clearly identified copyrighted source, and that, in some cases at least, it must remain non-pornographic.

⁹³ Jenkins, Henry. *Transforming Fan Culture into User-Generated Content: The Case of FanLib*. <http://www.henryjenkins.org/2007/05/transforming_fan_culture_into.html>, [22.05.07], [accessed 11.06.07]

As mentioned previously, author Anne Rice is well-known as being unequivocally against fanfiction and in 1999 sent a number of C&D letters to fan sites containing fanfiction based on her books. In 2001 a C&D letter was sent to major fanfiction archive 'Fanfiction.net' demanding that all Anne Rice fanfiction be removed⁹⁴. A number of other authors have also requested that 'Fanfiction.net' remove any stories based on their copyrighted material, including Robin Hobb, Laurell K. Hamilton, Nora Roberts and Raymond Feist.

In 1997 author Anne McCaffrey sent a C&D letter to a website containing fanfiction based on her *Dragonriders of Pern* series, although McCaffrey has since altered her stance on fanfiction and now permits fanfiction based on her novels as long as they abide by a number of guidelines⁹⁵.

There are very few instances of legal action being threatened as a result of commercial activity on the part of fans, largely because most fans have no interest in making money from their creative endeavours and recognise that attempting to do would put them in a very risky legal position. The first instance took place in 1977 when Paramount sent a C&D letter to a *Star Trek* fanzine, mistakenly believing it to be a professional publication. The matter was dropped when the misapprehension came to light.

More recently, a *Star Wars* fanfiction 'novel' was being offered for sale by a fanfiction author named Lori Jareo through Amazon, Barnes & Noble and Powell's print-on-demand services. There was an immense backlash against Jareo amongst the fanfiction community, with many fans fearing that Jareo's action could impel many copyright holders to rethink their tolerance towards fanfiction. Once the matter came to the attention of Lucasfilm the book was pulled from all three websites as well as the author's personal website, although as yet no formal legal action has been taken.

⁹⁴ *Where Has Anne Rice Fanfiction Gone?* <<http://www.angelfire.com/rant/croatoan/>>, [n.d.], accessed 17.06.07]

⁹⁵ McCaffrey, Anne. *The Worlds of Anne McCaffrey*. <http://www.annemccaffrey.net/index.php?page_id=20>, [n.d.], [accessed 03.06.07]

Many of the examples of warnings based on adult or pornographic material have come as a result of *Harry Potter* fanfiction, although Lucasfilm began issuing warnings to *Star Wars* fanzines which published sexually explicit stories as far back as 1981⁹⁶. In 2002 adult *Harry Potter* fanfiction archives ‘Restricted Section’ and ‘Potter Slash Archive’ were both sent C&D letters as a result of adult material⁹⁷. In 2003 lawyers acting for J.K. Rowling sent a C&D letter to a *Harry Potter* website containing adult fanfiction and fan-art run by a fan in Australia, demanding that the material be removed⁹⁸. The website in question is now no longer accessible.

In 2002 ‘Fanfiction.net’ instituted a ‘no adult fanfiction’ policy in a pre-emptive attempt to forestall any kind of legal activity based on adult material, a long-sighted decision considering the sheer amount of Harry Potter fanfiction in the archive and in light of the legal activity that came later that year.

There are doubtless more examples of C&D letters issued than are listed here; however, it must be stressed that the numbers of legal warnings issued against fanfiction have been exceptionally few, especially when compared to the vast amount of fanfiction available online.

⁹⁶ Jenkins, Henry. *Convergence Culture*, p. 142

⁹⁷ Chilling Effects Clearinghouse.

<<http://www.chillingeffects.org/fanfic/notice.cgi?NoticeID=522>>, [n.d.], [accessed 07.06.07]

⁹⁸ Chilling Effects Clearinghouse.

<<http://www.chillingeffects.org/fanfic/notice.cgi?NoticeID=534>>, [n.d.], [accessed 07.06.07]

Chapter 4

The Fans

4.1 Why Fans Write Fanfiction

Fanfiction has been described by academics in a multitude of ways: as a modern reinvention of communal oral storytelling or as a reaction against corporate ownership of culture, as a means of exploring often taboo subjects such as homosexuality and incest or as a subversive feminist community resisting patriarchal censorship and disapproval. Yet the overwhelming majority of fanfiction participants would not describe it in these terms, would probably not even think of it in these terms.

For these writers, there are a number of impulses prompting them to write fanfiction and almost none of them fit into many academics' tidy categories. As one writer explained, she read and wrote fanfiction for a number of reasons:

“partly out of love for the canon material and a desire for more; a chance to explore areas canon won't; a source of fantastic, well-written literature; a chance to write in a very particular kind of context, in terms of the reading community; a source of woman-friendly porn; a medium which gives me access to a community of like-minded people”⁹⁹

To this list could be added the opportunity to improve writing skills and a source of instant, constructive supportive feedback.

4.1.1 Love

The starting impulse for any fanfiction writer is love. It may seem like a patently obvious statement, but all too many seem to underestimate the 'fan' aspect of

⁹⁹ Text in italics here and subsequently indicates a quote from a questionnaire response.

fanfiction, looking for overly-complex desires and impulses to suit underlying sociological and ethnographic theories. Fans write fanfiction because they are fans, because, as Philomena Guinea (Dark Roast)¹⁰⁰ wrote in the questionnaire devised for this dissertation, *“If I really love a movie or series, I can't get enough of that world. I want to interact with it more deeply.”* These combined desires, to interact with and wish for more of the much-loved material of a book, film or television show, are the primary impulses behind the reading and writing of fanfiction.

There are many aspects of a book, film or television show that draw fans in: an exciting or intriguing plot, the exploration of social and political issues, the high standard of acting, writing and directing, but it is the characters that inspire love: *“mysterious or ambiguous but compelling characters”, “well-rounded characters with ‘gaps’ in the story that need filling”, “characters who seem to have more to say to each other than what they have said on the page/screen”*. Almost 70% of respondents stated that it was primarily the characters and their relationships that impelled them to write fanfiction.

Fans tend to become very emotionally attached to characters, especially when dealing with television or book series, where the characters’ lives and relationships can be explored in much greater detail over a longer period of time. As Riona wrote, *“if I've fallen in love with a world or characters, I might not be prepared to let go of them when the canon ends.”* Fiercynn wrote:

“When I read or watch books, comics, movies, and TV shows, I tend to latch onto characters and fall for them completely. I get completely obsessed and want to get as much from the characters and stories as I can - which usually results in reading or writing fanfiction.”

The overwhelming majority of fanfiction available online concerns character dynamics generally referred to as ‘ships’, short for ‘relationships’. For many fans their feelings about the source material, whether it be a book or film, are

¹⁰⁰ Names used here and subsequently are pen names or pseudonyms and are rendered exactly as provided by the participants, spelling and capitalisation included.

intrinsically bound up with their feelings about these ships. Their love for the source material can rise and fall in direct correspondence to the canon treatment of their beloved characters and pairings, not all of which are supported in the canon. Many fans have been known to abandon a show altogether because their ‘ship has been sunk’, either because a character has been killed, written out or paired up with another character. Fans can also become immensely possessive and defensive over these ships: the ‘ship wars’ in the *Harry Potter* fandom between supporters of Ron/Hermione and Harry/Hermione are quite infamous and eventually reverberated all the way up to the attention of J. K. Rowling herself. This issue of fans’ possessiveness will be explored in more detail subsequently.

As demonstrated by the aforementioned Philomena Guinea (Dark Roast)’s words, one of the most common explanations given for reading and writing fanfiction is the desire for ‘more’: more material, more time with the characters, more adventures or romance than the official product provides:

“I suppose the short answer is that I want more than what's available from the original creator.”

“Because I like the universes and the characters therein so much I want more!”

“If I really love a show or a book or comic or whatever, I tend to want more: more new episodes more often. Fanfic is a good way to get a supplement, as it were.”

This desire for more explains why nearly 64% of respondents had bought officially licensed tie-in novels in the past, despite 79% of that number rating the quality of the tie-in novels as somewhere between poor and average. Anything officially produced, however poor in quality, is devoured by fans, and if no more is forthcoming, fans take it upon themselves to create more:

“I have a great love for a particular work of fiction. The author of this body of work is now dead, which means that the canon body of work will not be expanded. However, the work has extreme breadth of scope in terms of characters, settings and dramatic situations, and also contains great universal themes that are worthy of further exploration. Part of my love of fanfiction in this universe [is] the continual exploration of these themes, part of it is a desire for more interaction and greater exploration of the characters and setting that I love.”

This explains why many fanfiction writers find the idea that fanfiction poses a threat to the official product mystifying. To fanfiction writers, fanfiction fills a hole in the market that is not being satisfied by the original product. It is not taking away custom; on the contrary, it is highlighting the fans’ demand for it.

4.1.2 Exploration & Freedom

Numerous fanfiction writers express the desire to ‘fill in the blanks’, to explore areas that the source material has failed to for whatever reason – a fact that is often recognised by the official representatives of the material. David Kemper, executive producer of *Farscape*, has been quoted as saying, “They’re [the fans] expanding the relationships into a place that we don’t have time to do on television”¹⁰¹.

Fans want to know what happened before the cameras started rolling, before the events in the book began, what happened when everything stopped and everything that wasn’t shown in-between:

“There are [...] lots of moments that get lost because of time constraints or because higher ups may not want to see certain storylines or ideas so reading/writing gives those moments life.”

¹⁰¹ Kemper, David. Cited in Werts, Diane. Adventures in cyberspace. *Milwaukee Journal Sentinel* [online], 10.05.05. <<http://www.jsonline.com/story/index.aspx?id=324712>>, [accessed 15.07.07]

“Examination of what could happen off the screen and/or behind the scenes of a book (depending on the fandom).”

“There are holes in the stories that need exploring, and character development/definition I need done for me to know the characters better.”

They want to know everything and no official canon could ever possibly satisfy this insatiable craving. As a result, the fans imagine it for themselves.

There are innumerable different genres of fanfiction stories all designed to elaborate upon, fill in or in some cases completely rewrite the canon: ‘vignettes’, short stand-alone stories, often consisting of ‘missing scenes’ between major events or a single character’s emotions; ‘codas’, similar to vignettes but comprising character-based epilogues to resolved plots; ‘POV’ or point-of-view stories, telling the same story as a book or film from a different perspective; ‘fix-its’, generally used to re-write canon when a much-loved character has been killed off or written out.

For example, bookworm927 said:

“It utterly fascinates me how a fanfic writer can take a world (for example, Harry Potterverse) and then look at it from a completely different angle than the original writer ever took - eg, the hundreds of fics set in the Marauders era (ie when Harry's parents were at school) and build a completely new perspective.”

Many fanfiction writers also enjoy changing the canon of a particular film or book: taking the characters out of their established contexts, switching the sex of characters, rewriting the back-story or taking the material in a new and often strange direction. As Ronald D. Moore, producer of *Battlestar Galactica*, said:

“I always loved it when writers went into strange nooks and crannies and turned the universe upside down in ways that we couldn't. 'Wouldn't it be

great if Kirk and Spock were lovers?' We can't do that, but it's great that somebody can.”¹⁰²

Once again, there are a number of different genres of fanfiction that fans use to ‘play’ with the canon in this way: AUs (short for ‘alternative universe’), where fans posit ‘what-if’ scenarios and often place characters in entirely different situations: Mulder and Scully in the Civil War, for example, or Harry Potter never going to Hogwarts; crossovers, where characters from one source interact with others from a completely different source: Superman meets Frodo or Buffy the Vampire Slayer on the Starship Enterprise; and crackfic, which are intentionally insane and ridiculous stories: Kirk and Spock waking up one morning having switched bodies or James Bond turns into a unicorn.

“I also enjoy utterly ridiculous fanfiction, aka crack fiction, just because it's fun to take established characters and turn their worlds upside-down.”

“I read and write because there are so many circumstances that the characters from shows and movies, created by other people, will never, ever find themselves in.”

“I write it because it's fun to play with characters and canon, and figure out how characters who've never met in canon would interact with each other, or what would happen if a canon event happened differently, or if the characters were in a different place/time altogether.”

Other writers enjoy taking the canon in directions it cannot or will not go in print or onscreen, exploring taboo or uncomfortable subjects or contentious social issues, to “bring in elements that exist in our culture but are artificially removed from visibility in most fiction (sex, alternate sex, the consequences of violence, the different ways people live)”, as one fanfiction writer put it. Fanfiction gives these writers the opportunity to write for the sheer joy of it, without having to

¹⁰² Moore, Ronald D. Cited in *ibid*.

pander to publishers, agents and audiences. They can write what they want to write, without having to think about whether the finished product will sell.

Polgarawolf, one of the most articulate and eloquent fanfiction writers surveyed, described how fanfiction allows her to explore *“characters’ impulses and motivations much more deeply than would be permitted in “romance novels or subgenre-flavor-of-the-year books”*:

“I [...] want to explore new possibilities and push at (and hopefully past) the boundaries of what society happens to think of as “acceptable” or “normal.” I honestly think that fanfiction is the best forum for doing all of that. Original work is fine and dandy, sure, but it basically has to sell to find an audience, doesn't it? That means compromise, in the process of getting a publishing company to sell it. That means pandering to the masses and to the biases of the masses. Why would a person who desires to write for the love of it and the sheer challenge it poses and the possibilities it opens do that, when it's possible to bypass that whole ugly mess of commercialism and marketability and conformity by writing something meaningful and unbounded by societal expectations for characters you already know and love?”

4.1.3 Community

The community aspect of fanfiction writing is very important to most writers. In the same way that publishers, editors and agents all work to support and enhance a professional writer’s work, the fanfiction community proves a safe, supportive environment for the fanfiction writer to work (or play) in.

It is also a somewhat underground community – the products of the community (i.e. the fanfiction itself) are accessible to almost all, but the actual community and its individual fandoms are more akin to private clubs with their own social structure and language, open only to those ‘in the know’. As one writer said, *“It’s an addictive underworld. You lift up the stone to see what’s underneath and oh my God, it’s seething under there.”*

Within the community many fans like to refer to themselves as ‘fen’ rather than ‘fans’, mainly to “differentiate it from the mainstream world’s derogatory use of the term. ‘Fans’, to rhyme with ‘sad and/or mad geeks’.”¹⁰³ Many fanfiction writers prefer to keep their fan activities a secret from friends, family and colleagues, mostly because they feel ‘outsiders’ would not understand. As Sheenagh Pugh has observed in her study of fanfiction, the lack of original characters and low value placed on genre fiction tends to lead many writers, academics and critics to view the writing of fanfiction with disdain¹⁰⁴.

This ‘us against them’ mindset can have a beneficial affect. As Pugh observes, “communities which feel beleaguered or misunderstood are generally close-knit”¹⁰⁵, and this is certainly the case with fanfiction. The private, almost exclusive nature and clannish mentality fosters a particular sense of community and friendship, as many fans recognise and value:

“I like the fellowship feeling of a fandom.”

“I feel part of a community of, predominately, women who feel [the same].”

“I love the community & fanon that makes it.”

This community and the individual fandoms within have an important social function quite apart from the day-to-day ‘fan business’. Many fans have made lasting friendships through their fanfiction and see the fanfiction community not just as a source of reading material but as a place to share interests:

“I enjoy the connections I’ve made with other fans through fanfiction.”

“I think fanfiction is an opportunity to connect with others. The feeling you get when you realise that someone watched or read something and then had

¹⁰³ Leia Fee. Cited in Sheenagh Pugh. *The Democratic Genre*, 2005, p. 118

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid.*

the same thoughts and ideas as you is brilliant, but it also works the other way too. It gives you a whole other perspective on things.”

“It's a way of sharing your interests with other people from across the world.”

As Henry Jenkins has written:

“What fandom offers is a community not defined in traditional terms of race, religion, gender, region, politics, or profession, but rather a community of consumers defined through their common relationship with shared texts. [...] Entering into fandom means abandoning pre-existing social status and seeking acceptance and recognition less in terms of who you are than in terms of what you contribute to this new community. Fandom is particularly attractive to groups marginalized or subordinated in the dominant culture – women, blacks, gay, lower-middle-class office workers, the handicapped – precisely because its social organization provides types of unconditional acceptance...”¹⁰⁶

It is not hard to see the appeal of the fanfiction community when viewed in these terms, nor why Sheenagh Pugh chose *The Democratic Genre* as the title for her study of fanfiction.

4.1.4 Literacy

The online fanfiction community is a good example of what James Gee has called ‘affinity spaces’, “a space where informal learning takes place, characterized by, among other things, the sharing of knowledge and expertise based on voluntary affiliations”.¹⁰⁷ Whilst perhaps not phrasing it in these terms, nearly 88% of writers surveyed believed that the reading and writing of

¹⁰⁶ Jenkins, Henry. “‘Strangers No More, We Sing’: Filking and the Social Construction of the Science Fiction Fan Community’, *The Adoring Audience*, 1992, p. 213.

¹⁰⁷ Jenkins, Henry. *Convergence Culture*, 2006, p.280

fanfiction had a beneficial effect on their own literacy, a fact a number of teachers and academics would agree with. Rebecca Black has argued that the

“networked structure of such sites facilitates...learning and promotes writing by providing ...access to a broad audience of readers and multiple community writing resources [and that] by highlighting the social and interactive nature of writing in this space, connections among language, literacy, and identity are emphasized.”¹⁰⁸

There is a highly structured system of review and feedback in places for almost all fanfiction, allowing readers to connect directly with writers, a system that Julianne Chatelain has suggested could be used a model for other online communities¹⁰⁹. Writers can build on this feedback, both positive and negative, and use it to improve their writing abilities. Many fanfiction writers also use ‘beta-readers’, who serve roughly the same roles as editors, reading and critiquing the story before ‘publication’. This is often a reciprocal relationship, allowing writers to develop their own editorial and critical skills.

Many writers comment on fanfiction as an easy way of learning to write, of coping with the constraints of a text and learning new ways to direct narrative and plot. The opportunity to use ‘ready-made characters that are already well fleshed-out’ is invaluable to many writers who feel they have a story to tell but struggle to develop the underlying structure necessary to impart the story:

“I write fanfiction because I sometimes find it difficult to come up with my own characters and scenarios.”

¹⁰⁸ Black, Rebecca. Abstract from Access and Affiliation: The Literacy and Composition Practices of English-Language Learners in an Online Fanfiction Community. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 49(2), 118–128.
<<http://www.reading.org/publications/journals/jaal/v49/i2/abstracts/JAAL-49-2-Black.html>>, [accessed 26.05.07]

¹⁰⁹ Chatelain, Julianne. *Learning from the Review Culture of Fan Fiction*.
<<http://jodi.ecs.soton.ac.uk/Articles/v03/i03-old/chatelain/fanfic.html>>, [n.d.], [accessed 05.06.07]

“I haven't got any original story plots, so I just used already created worlds, and characters, and maybe even plots, to try and shape my writing style, and more aspects about writing.”

“I also write fanfiction as practice, that way you use characters and universes previously developed and learn to stick to those rules, while you create your own characters and universes inside them to see how real they can get.”

This idea that fanfiction can serve as an educational tool, as well as a source of community and entertainment, is one that is gaining ground amongst academics and may well help fanfiction in its legal struggle. A number of fanfiction writers cited the example of teachers who required students to compose their own endings to set texts for homework, believing the same principle could apply to fanfiction.

Many fanfiction writers are still young, still developing their literary skills, and fanfiction can serve as an invaluable educational tool, especially for those writers for whom English is not their first language:

“[It helps] to make my writing skills - grammar in particular - better. I like to do things I am not particularly good at as hobbies because I get great pride when I improve. And writing is one of those categories.”

4.1.5 Sexuality

A large amount of fanfiction online is adult erotica, quite frequently slash. A great deal of academic time has been spent investigating what prompts women – for the majority of fanfiction writers are female – to spend so much time and effort writing about two ostensibly heterosexual characters of the same sex having sexual relations. Perhaps the answer is somewhat simpler than many academics realise. Just as many men find the idea of lesbians sexually titillating,

so too do many women find the reverse concept just as exciting: what Henry Jenkins has described as “normal female interest in men bonking”.¹¹⁰

One fan explained the appeal of slash and other sexually explicit fanfiction using just one word: ‘jouissance’, an interesting and in this context particularly apt French term that has three particular meanings: “an extreme or deep pleasure; sexual orgasm; and in law, having the right to use something”¹¹¹.

Another wrote, *“I read slash mainly - men in homoerotic relationships because it's romantic, hot and socially engaging.”* This statement largely encapsulates the attraction of slash for many fans – and it surely not difficult to see why this would appeal to so many heterosexual women.

However, it is not just heterosexual women who find slash appealing. As mentioned above the fanfiction community is very often a haven for marginalised societal groups for whom fanfiction presents the opportunity to reflect their own interests and desires onto the predominantly heterosexual narrative. As bookgrrrl wrote, *“As a queer woman who does not see reflections of her life or sexuality portrayed on screen often, or accurately, I use fanfiction to queer the narrative, to make a space in which subtext can become maintext.”*

Other fans feel that fanfiction, in its bending of gender roles and stereotypes and its flexible sexual roles, is subverting the conventional societal tendency to label and categorise sexuality:

“I happen to believe that labels involving such things as gender, sexuality, sexual orientation, sexual identity, etc., are all primarily artificial constructs created and enforced by societies and cultures as a way to try to regulate and normalize individuals by rendering qualities that are individual-specific and liable to change with the passage of time and the alteration of circumstances into static, rigidly defined, unchanging (unalterable), and

¹¹⁰ Jenkins, Henry. ‘Normal Female Interest in Men Bonking’, *Theorizing Fandom*, 1998, p. 9

¹¹¹ Clark, Robert. ‘Jouissance’, *The Literary Encyclopedia*.

<<http://www.litencyc.com/php/stopics.php?rec=true&UID=602>>, [01.01.04], [accessed 23.07.07]

therefore controllable universal aspects of being so that they can then be used to quantify and categorize certain types of people and so assign specific functions and ranges of use to those types for the societies/cultures in question[...] Really good fanfiction avoids or otherwise explodes (or at least attempts to seriously undermine) the trap of socially constructed artificial labels in ways that most 'pro' fic is apparently too scared or too materialistic to even try to do."

Sonia Katyal agrees with this viewpoint in her article 'Performance, Property, and the Slashing of Gender in Fan Fiction', stating that "slash fan fiction empowers the virtual community to actively rework traditional narratives between men, demonstrating how queering mainstream characters can actually deconstruct, and then transcend, traditional gender norms and stereotypes."¹¹²

4.2 Perceptions of Ownership

That fans get highly possessive and protective of the source material of their infatuation is not in any doubt. Over 96% of fans surveyed agreed that they had frequently felt anger and dissatisfaction at a show's creator or writer when the material was taken in a direction they did not agree with and 94% agreed that fans tend to get immensely possessive over the source material of their fandom, whether it is book, film or TV show. The important question for this dissertation is why? What leads fans to these feelings of ownership and entitlement?

Many fans claimed that they could not understand the logic behind such emotional responses or that there was no logic to it and it was a purely irrational emotional impulse. But several themes did emerge from the responses collected in the survey that elucidates the fans' thinking and may help to explain this possessive impulse.

¹¹² Katyal, Sonia. Performance, Property, and the Slashing of Gender in Fan Fiction. *Journal of Gender, Social Policy, and the Law* [online], 2006, 14(3), p. 461-518.
<<http://www.wcl.american.edu/journal/genderlaw/14/katyal3.pdf?rd=1>>, [accessed 15.07.07]

One of the most frequently used terms in explaining the fans' possessiveness was 'human nature'. Elspethdixon wrote that, "*it's human nature to feel some degree of ownership/possessiveness for anything we love*", whilst ksl believes that "*it's not just fans as we define them in fandom. Even the average viewer experiences this, for their favorite shows. The viewing audience has never been as passive as the product creators would like to think. We all take ownership, to one degree or another.*"

Baked Goldfish compared the impulse to that of sports fans, stating:

"sports fans may be possessive or defensive of their favorite teams/players, want to see them succeed and want to see them get positive recognition, because they might feel as though they are 'one of the team' or a part of the family. It is possibly the same for media fans."

The analogy with sports fans is quite apt. Although very few football fans have any direct connection with the football club or the players, it is still 'their' club and they demonstrate their affiliation by purchasing merchandise and attending games. Their support of their chosen team, in many ways, defines their existence, at least in football terms. In the same way, fans 'choose' an affiliation, namely 'their' fandom, and participate in it, display that affiliation by purchasing merchandise, attending conventions and watching or reading the source material. In the same way that football supporters do, fans suffer through the lows and rejoice in the highs and always have an opinion on the events that are taking place, whether that opinion be positive or negative.

This ties into another theme that emerged from the survey: the idea that the fans feel they deserve some kind of return on the time and effort they have invested into the fandom and that this sense of entitlement is expressed through feelings of possessiveness. Nearly 99% of fans questioned believed that TV shows, movies or books benefited from having a large and passionate fan base: if this is true, it is not hard to see why fans may feel they are entitled to something more than simply being permitted to watch or read the official material:

“Because of all the emotions and time we've put into a fandom, it's not hard to feel that you 'own' it to a certain extent. We expect that because we've done so much for it, it would reward us with what we like about it.”

“We're investing a lot of time, energy, and thought into these things. It makes sense that we should feel some sense of ownership, or betrayal when things don't go our way.”

“A fan, as opposed to a more casual reader/viewer, devotes extensive time and attention to the source material. Consequently, I think it's only natural to feel a strong degree of investment and desire some sort of return on that investment.”

Other fans also felt that the emotional investment and identification that is an inherent part of fandom naturally leads to feelings of ownership and possession. As Calysta Rose said, *“We, fans, become emotionally invested in these characters. We bring them home, so to speak, and live with them. It's only natural that we become protective and possessive of them.”* Suzanne wrote that fans are inherently more likely to invest in characters than ‘normal’ readers or viewers:

“Media studies scholars have argued that the object of one's fannish affection is no longer properly exterior to one's Self. Rather, it is located on the threshold of Self and world in the manner of a transitional object.”

The fans latch onto particular characters for a variety of reasons, many of which are deeply personal. Some fans personally identify with characters; others see them as role models or heroes, something to aspire to be. For some fans, the characters can have real-life reflections and provide a fictional environment in which to work through emotional issues: as one fan wrote, *“I had some serious emotional problems and I got involved with characters because they were so much like my dysfunctional family of origin.”*

Whatever the reasoning, fans do get deeply emotionally involved with characters and this can lead to very strong negative emotions if the characters are taken in directions that the fans do not like:

“Fans get invested in the characterizations ... and when the IP [intellectual property] holders take the character or ship in an unexpected direction, some fans revolt.”

“If I identify with a character I find myself getting extremely attached to them, and any direction the writer's take them in that seems to fall outside the spectrum of their usual character's direction is like separating the viewer from themselves, in a way. If you identify with a character so much because you can imagine yourself in their situation, it's easy to get annoyed or be angry when they go in a direction you wouldn't go in yourself.”

“Often, without realising, they [fans] feel such a connection that they treat the character as a sort of "avatar" of themselves. Thus, any perceived injustice to the character- attaching it to the "wrong" person, or causing it to behave in a way inconsistent with a fan's view of the character- is (unconsciously in most cases) perceived as a personal slight.”

Some fans explained how characters come to be more than real to them: 99 bottles of rum described them as *“your friends, your children and you want only what you think is best for them”*; Ro Anshi felt they become an *“internal family”*; whilst to scatesi characters were *“personal friends whose communications are limited to a series of video postcards or letters ‘to whom it may concern’”*. Viewing the characters in this way leads fans to react the canon developments on a very personal level. As scatesi went on to say,

“It is no longer about an imaginary character but about them, the reader/viewer, and their relationships. They will no more condone a character not finding a fulfilling relationship than they would their baby sister dating a serial killer as much because they want the character, as a friend, to be happy as because they want to know that they themselves can

find something similar, where the wrongs are righted and those who deserve a happy ending will most assuredly find one.”

The writing of fanfiction itself can lead to feeling of ownership over the characters. As Catherine wrote, *“I think people forget that they don't actually ‘own’ the particular character or relationship. They're so used to being able to do what they want with them...”* Aliasagent elaborated on this, saying:

“you get possessive over characters because even though you borrow them from the fandom, you still tweak them a bit and in order to write them you have to try and see the levels and layers of the character. The understanding you get when you write a character contributes to the possessiveness.”

This possessiveness over writing the character is amplified when dealing with minor characters or aspects of the source material that have not been explored in great depth:

“Especially if they're non-canon, we invented them [the ships], we saw the subtext (or not), and we support them. If they're not specifically in canon, they're pretty much ours.”

“When there is a less well-defined character in particular, the fandom loves to fill in the gaps the writers leave. As such, people can get very possessive of their personal canon when there is no actual canon to fall back on.”

“Canon is open to interpretation, especially once you move beyond the boundaries of 'gapfillers' into stories with original characters or alternative universe genres. Especially in a closed canon (not currently being written by the original author) not all possible scenarios will be addressed. People writing and reading fanfiction are passionately interested in their fandom. They usually, but not always, take pride to carefully examine the source material for insights about the personalities of their characters and particularities of their setting. Taken together, this leads them to be possessive about the conclusions they have made and written.”

The writing itself leads to thoughts of ownership, for the characters exist in the fanfiction writer's head as much as that of the original author and very often in a somewhat different form, since all individuals interpret things differently:

“Fans are active readers and meaning-makers. A given fan will likely be just as emotionally invested in the particular interpretation of a character or pairing that she has made as the initial author is invested in the versions inside her/his head. Which is to say: very. Both are acts of creation, and just about everyone wants to believe their creations are valid and primary.”

Indeed, nearly 84% of fans questioned believed that they wrote characters as they interpreted them and not as the author intended them. As a result, it is not necessarily the canon that fans are claiming emotional ownership over. It is the fanon they might justifiably claim ownership over, the fanon that has been constructed from their own backgrounds and cultures, shaped by their own emotions and ideologies, populated by their own interpretations of characters and expressed through their own imaginations.

4.3 Legal Awareness and Reactions

As mentioned previously, the fanfiction community is surprisingly self-aware and there are a number of debates in many circles on the legality of fanfiction. Whilst very few fanfiction writers are lawyers, many are surprisingly informed on the intricacies of copyright law, although perhaps this is a consequence of the uncertainty of their position.

When asked, nearly 73% of respondents stated that they did not believe fanfiction constituted a violation of copyright, for a variety of reasons, the most prominent of which was fanfiction's non-profit status:

“It isn't illegal unless you make a try to profit from it.”

“Copyright law prohibits making a profit using copyrighted characters. As long as there is no profit made, there is no issue.”

“No money gained, no copyright infringement.”

Many others felt that fanfiction fell under the fair use clause of copyright law:

“It is a non-profit, altered work and falls under the fair use provisions.”

“I believe it falls into "fair use," especially as it has perpetuated the commercial viability of the source material.”

“My understanding is that if the writing is not done for profit and is done with the acknowledgement of the primary creator's prior claim then the fanfic author is covered either by fair use or parody rules.”

Several writers also argued that since, under UK copyright law at least, characters could not be copyrighted, there could be no copyright infringement in using them.

One of the most common beliefs expressed was that including a disclaimer at the head of any published fanfiction would protect the work from copyright infringement. 39% of writers questioned believed that such a disclaimer ought to protect fans, whilst a further 48% felt that it ought to, as long as certain caveats were met, such as remaining non-profit:

“As long as there is a disclaimer saying that the characters are not your own I can't see any real harm.”

“I wouldn't imagine it would be illegal if there's a clear disclaimer that the characters are not the property of the fanfiction author.”

Interestingly enough, there is case law to support this belief: in *Karll v. Curtis Publishing Co.*, the court ruled that the defendant's printing of several verses of a

song without permission constituted fair use since the defendant explicitly attributed authorship of the song to the plaintiff¹¹³; and in *Consumers Union of the United States, Inc. v. General Signal Corp.*¹¹⁴, where the court ruled a disclaimer was, in the words of Meredith McCardle, a “valid and productive means by which defendants can distance themselves from the plaintiff’s ownership interests.”¹¹⁵

15% of writers questioned claimed to have known fans involved in legal action, although it is clear from the responses that almost none of those questioned were personally involved themselves and most of their knowledge is based on hearsay. A number cited fairly well-known examples, such as the *Star Wars* fanzines or the *Harry Potter* archives. In almost every case, the result was a ‘victory’ for the copyright holder.

When faced with the threat of legal action from a multimillion dollar media corporation or publishing firm there is unfortunately very little an individual fan can do. Regardless of how strong their legal position may be, the average fan simply does not have the finances to take on the corporations in court and the number of law firms willing to take on such a case pro bono is small indeed. Almost all fans, when in such position, have backed down and acquiesced to any demands made upon them. There are, however, a number who have refused to bow to corporate intimidation and intriguingly in almost all of these cases it is the corporation who has backed down.

The two best-known examples involve *Harry Potter* fanfiction archives – ‘The Restricted Section’ and the ‘Potter Slash Archive’. Both archives were sent cease-and-desist letters as a result of adult content and both resisted the demands. Working with the assistance of the Chilling Effects Clearinghouse, the archives worked out a settlement with Rowling and Warner Brothers whereby access to

¹¹³ *Karll vs. Curtis Publishing Co.*, 51 U.S.P.Q.[E.D., Wisc., 1941]

¹¹⁴ *Consumers Union of United States, Inc. v. General Signal Corp.*, 724 F.2d 1044 [2d Cir. 1983]

¹¹⁵ McCardle, Meredith. Fandom, Fan Fiction, and Fanfare: What's All the Fuss?, *Boston University Journal of Science and Technology Law* [online], 2003, 9(2). <<http://www.bu.edu/law/central/jd/organizations/journals/scitech/volume92/mccardle.pdf>>, [accessed 03.05.07]

the offending material can now only be gained via a password system that is contingent on satisfying the age requirements. The archives also took steps to render the sites untraceable by search engine.

The Chilling Effects Clearinghouse is a joint project between the Electronic Frontier Foundation and a number of US law schools designed to resist the “deterrent effect of legal threats or posturing, largely cease and desist letters independent of litigation or lawful conduct.”¹¹⁶ It collects examples of cease-and-desist letters for analysis by legal professionals in order to provide legal education and assistance for the recipients – its database currently holds 2150 such letters. It also collects articles, news and case reports on pertinent issues from around the web and periodically issues ‘weather reports’ summing up the climate for online activity and highlighting areas of particular action.

4.4 Self-Regulation and the Rules of Engagement

One of the most interesting aspects of fanfiction and the fanfiction community is its attempts to regulate and restrict its own activities in order to remain low-profile and ‘below the radar’. As Billie Cameron wrote, *“There are rules within fandom that should be followed not because they are a law (they aren't), but out of respect for fellow readers and a sense of morality.”*

When surveyed, 82% felt that it was important for the fanfiction community to remain low-profile in order to survive. Fans are aware that their activities are, if not strictly legal or illegal, operating in an area which is dubious at best and subject to the legal intimidation of major media corporations with vastly superior legal resources at their command. As a result fans wish their activities to remain discreet and harmless enough to avoid attention:

“As long as copyright is still exclusive, anyone playing with someone else's toys needs to be quiet about it so they don't get slapped.”

¹¹⁶ Chilling Effects Clearinghouse. <<http://www.chillingeffects.org/faq.cgi>>, [n.d.], [accessed 07.06.07]

“We all play nicely in the creator's sandbox, and the creator is willing to loan us their toys as long as we don't go selling them or making blatant copies of them.”

“Keeping under the radar is always the best plan, even in the face of some creators who seem to be indifferent to, amenable to or actively fond of their fans and fan works.”

Controlling access to fanfiction is important to many fans. 44% of fans surveyed only published their fanfiction on their own personal online journals or blogs, many of which can be ‘friends-locked’, ensuring only acknowledged and known individuals can access the content. 31% published their fanfiction in online archives, many of which, as mentioned previously, are password-protected and some are even un-Googleable. This latter aspect was a requirement in the settlement that allowed adult *Harry Potter* fanfiction archive ‘The Restricted Section’ to remain online. Unfortunately this still leaves a vast amount of fanfiction freely available online: as mentioned earlier, a Google search for fanfiction lists over 6 million results.

Almost all fanfiction online, whether published privately or on a public website or archive, contains a disclaimer, usually at the very head of the story, that disavows any legal authority on the part of the fanfiction author, makes it plain no profit is being made clearly and names the owners of the copyrighted material. Many fanfiction archives make it a requirement of publication that a disclaimer be included. As mentioned previously, the inclusion of a disclaimer will not provide any specific legal protection, but it can prove useful in inclining a copyright holder or legal representation to look somewhat more benevolently on fanfiction writers’ activities.

However, the ‘golden rule’ of fanfiction, the one rule that all fanfiction writers feel must be obeyed and that garners the most vitriolic criticism when violated, is the not-for-profit rule. It is the fact that fanfiction is strictly not-for-profit that prompts many copyright holders to permit or at the very least turn a blind eye to

its current existence and it this fact that will likely garner the most legal protection should the matter ever come before a court of law.

One of the greatest fears in fandom is that it would only take one fan to go too far and cause one of the major media corporations or publishers to go beyond C&D letters in actual legal action. Should this ever occur it is likely that the resulting decision would have an enormous effect on the fanfiction community and irrevocably change its nature and structure forever. It is likely that should such a situation ever occur it will largely be a result of financial concerns. Many fans, for example, were extremely concerned that the aforementioned Lori Jareo incident, where a fan was selling her *Star Wars* fanfiction on Amazon and other print-on-demand websites, would lead to such a case.

As a result most fans are extremely scathing and critical of those individuals who appear to violate these unwritten rules. Many used terms as such ‘pathetic’, ‘silly’, ‘reprehensible’ and ‘disrespectful’ and stated that they would shun the individual and their fanfiction in future. Baked Goldfish wrote, “*They embarrass me and draw unnecessary and dangerous attention to fandom as a whole*”, and ksl felt that such individuals were “*putting fandom at risk for the sake of their own egos*”.

These unwritten rules help to explain why the fanfiction community greeted the unveiling of FanLib.com, a new ‘official’ fanfiction website with such scepticism and dismay. With \$3 million worth of funding from famous names in Hollywood and with partnerships in place with HarperCollins, Penguin Books, Simon & Schuster and Starz Entertainment, FanLib’s aim is to bring fanfiction into the mainstream and allow fans greater contact with the creators of the shows and movies that inspired the fanfiction in the first place. Many fans do not see it in such positive terms, feeling that it is merely a

“pernicious collection of contradictions and legal naïveté ... interested primarily in grabbing as much of the profit as they can squeeze out of other people’s creative works while ducking any possible legal responsibility should any of the copyright holders send their lawyers around.”

82% of fans surveyed stated that they would not publish at FanLib, largely because it is such a high-profile, well-publicised endeavour taking place in an environment where for almost forty years remaining low-profile has ensured survival. Fans also feel that FanLib's funding and lucrative advertising and sponsorship deals could leave it, and by extension the fans publishing there, at risk of legal action. FanLib might not be making money directly from the fanfiction but it is making money as a result of the existence of the fanfiction it hosts, and many fans do not wish to be anywhere near such a legally dubious operation. For most fans *"it's just not cricket - it goes against the fundamental feeling of community that's at the heart of good fanfiction. It should be (and generally is) a group of people who love a particular universe so much that they just want to play in it for a little longer"* and not for financial reasons.

Conclusions

Fanfiction is rapidly becoming a victim of its own success. Its massive growth has led to more and more awareness of its existence amongst mainstream media producers and consumers. This growth has meant that fanfiction can no longer remain unobserved – it no longer occupies such a small corner of the World Wide Web. Fanfiction is being noticed and, for many fans, this is not necessarily a good thing.

Henry Jenkins argues that the fanfiction community is part of a wider online community that is in the process of constructing its own *sub rosa* culture, not of “borrowed remnants snatched from mass culture, but their own culture built from the semiotic raw materials the media provides”.¹¹⁷ Fans feel that they have a right to use this material, that a society’s cultural produce cannot and should not belong to any one individual or corporation. The copyright holders, of course, would disagree.

The conflict arises from a fundamental difference in the way mass culture is viewed. For the fans, as Jenkins writes,

“Once television characters enter into a broader circulation, intrude into our living rooms, pervade the fabric of our society, they belong to their audience and not simply to the artists who originated them. Media texts, thus, can and must be remade by their viewers so that potentially significant materials can better speak to their audience’s cultural interests and more fully address their desires.”¹¹⁸

For the copyright holders, on the other hand, television, and by extension, film and book characters are commodities, products, sources of financial wealth that are bought and sold, exploited and owned.

¹¹⁷ Henry, Jenkins. *Textual Poachers*, 1992, p. 49

¹¹⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 279

However, without the fans these cultural products have no value to be exploited, in both emotional and economic terms, and value can only be invested by the fans. Jenkins uses the old story ‘The Velveteen Rabbit’ as a metaphor for fans’ use of material. In the story it is only through being loved over a long period of time, picked up and tossed aside again and incorporated into games and fantasies that the velveteen rabbit can become real. From the toymaker’s perspective, the rabbit’s wear and tear - the threadbare fur, the loose eye - is a sign of vandalism and misuse, but for the child these are all traces of loving use. It is only through this use that the rabbit can become real.

In the same way, whilst copyright holders may see the fans’ use of their material as vandalism, as intellectual property infringement or wanton destruction, it is an activity based in loving use and, as Jenkins writes, these texts “assume significance as they are fragmented and reworked to accommodate the particular interests of the individual”.¹¹⁹ If the writers or creators want their work to live in the minds of their audience, to assume significance and become ‘real’, then the price is a little wear and tear of the material. It is the fans’ emotional valuing of the material that gives it its financial value.

If the online fan community is indeed constructing its own culture from the raw material of the mass media then it is not simply the individual fanfiction stories that are transformative but also the entire framework the stories are constructed within. It is the difficulty in separating out the stories from the culture they were created within that has given rise to the problems of intellectual property rights that fanfiction faces.

Until such time as a case involving fanfiction ever comes before a court of law, either in the US or the UK, these problems will likely continue. As this study shows, there are very good legal arguments that could be brought to bear on behalf of fanfiction writers should a dispute ever get that far. As the situation currently stands both sides have a vested interest in ensuring that no case involving fanfiction ever comes before a judge. Both fanfiction writers and

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 51

copyright holders have too much to lose should the case go against them – fanfiction writers worry that a definitive ruling against fanfiction will lead to open season against fanfiction writers and copyright holders fear the loss of control and earnings should fanfiction be ruled as permissible under copyright law.

What is clear is that copyright law is failing to address the needs and requirements of the age in which we now live. The 1976 Copyright Act and the 1988 Copyright, Designs and Patents Act were drawn up in a time before the World Wide Web was dreamed of; when lawmakers could have had no conception of the copyright and intellectual property rights problems such a development could pose. The proliferation of digital media technology has been progressing at such a pace that the law is in danger of being left behind - an archaic and ultimately extraneous law that has no relevance in modern society. Indeed, when questioned on this very subject, 90% of fanfiction writers believed the copyright law desperately needs to evolve to meet the requirements of the modern computer age.

Perhaps the West needs to learn from the Japanese example – *dōjinshi*, roughly akin to fanfiction, is not strictly legal; however, whilst the Japanese government does crack down on media piracy, it has largely left *dōjinshi* alone, recognising that “creativity doesn't fall from the sky. It needs nurturing, inspiration, tools and skills; and it's no problem if your inspiration is something cool someone else did first.”¹²⁰

As we have seen, the reading and writing of fanfiction can have a great many advantages: not merely in literacy, but in furthering social understanding and acceptance for marginalized groups, and providing a supportive and sympathetic environment for writers of all ages and levels. Fanfiction may well be blazing a trail towards a new understanding of the benefits of virtual learning environments and participatory culture. In the long-term these benefits may well

¹²⁰ Granick, Jennifer. Harry Potter Loves Malfoy, *Wired Magazine* [online]. <<http://www.wired.com/politics/law/commentary/circuitcourt/2006/08/71597>>, [16.08.06], [accessed 15.06.07].

prove enough to overcome any reservations copyright holders may have concerning issues of ownership and usage rights. In the short-term, the fans are here, and they are vocal and passionate, and they are not going away. The copyright holders of the world may find it necessary to come to terms with these fans in order to sustain their own existence.

Appendices

1 Glossary

Anime:

Abbreviation of the term ‘animation’. In this context, it refers to Japanese film and television animation.

Canon:

In fiction, the canon are those novels, television programs or films that are considered officially sanctioned and produced, as opposed to ‘fanon’, which refers to elements of a fictional world which are not part of the official canon but are widely treated by fans as though they were.

Cease & Desist:

Cease-and-desist letters are used under US law to demand the cessation of a particular activity. They are not legally binding in and of themselves and tend therefore to act as a warning of impending or potential legal action should the specified activity not be suspended.

Dôjinshi:

‘*Dôjinshi*’ is roughly the Japanese equivalent of fanfiction, referring to self-published, derivative works, often manga or novels.

Fandom:

‘Fandom’ is the term used to refer to a particular subculture of fans centred around any activity or interest, such as the *Harry Potter* or *Star Trek* fandoms, for example.

Fanfiction:

Fanfiction is unofficial, unauthorised, derivative, freeform, non-profit fiction written by fans of the original material, in a variety of styles and forms.

Fanzine:

A fanzine is an unofficial, fan-produced magazine focused on a particular fandom, often including fanfiction, fan art, poetry and articles.

Feedback:

There is a strong review culture within fanfiction and almost all fanfiction stories contain links for e-mails addresses or message boards where critical feedback can be left for the author.

Livejournal:

A virtual community made up of blogs supported by open-source software. Blogs on Livejournal can be private, individual blogs or community blogs with option open or closed memberships. Livejournal's demographics suggest it appeals to a more mature audience than MySpace.

Manga:

'Manga' is the Japanese term for comics and print cartoons. In this context, it refers specifically to Japanese comics.

Mary-Sue:

The term 'Mary-Sue' describes fanfiction that incorporates an original character that is a thinly-veiled idealised version of the author inserted into the story alongside their favourite characters and generally exhibits a number of clichéd characteristics: for example, a beautiful, instantly-likeable young woman with a tragic past, who saves the day and with whom the hero falls in love.

Profic:

'Pro-fic' is a term used to describe officially-licensed tie-in novels based on film and television programs that otherwise share many of the features of fanfiction.

Ships:

‘Ships’, short for ‘relationships’, refers to fans’ interest in and involvement with a particular pairing of characters within a fandom: Harry/Ginny, for example, or Kirk/Spock. Ships do not necessarily need to be supported by canon – indeed, a great number of the most popular ships are not supported by canon at all and many fans rely on subtext to justify their choice of ship.

Slash:

‘Slash’ refers to fanfiction focusing on the sexual and romantic relationship between two male characters, who are not necessarily homosexual or engaged in a canon relationship. The term comes from the ‘/’ used in the description of the pairing and is believed to arise originally from the Kirk/Spock fanfiction in the *Star Trek* fandom.

‘The Powers That Be’:

‘The Powers That Be’ or TPTB is a term used by fans to refer to the individuals that hold power over a particular fandom, specifically the corporate ‘overlords’, rather than the writers, directors etc.

2 Survey Text

Who Owns What in Fanfiction: Perceptions of Ownership and Problems of Law

I am a student at Loughborough University, studying for an MA in Library & Information Management. As part of my final year dissertation entitled 'Who Owns What in Fanfiction: Perceptions of Ownership & Problems of Law' I am investigating the opinions of fanfic authors/readers in regard to perceptions of ownership relating to fanfiction and its legal status or lack thereof.

I will not be requiring any personal details from you, save for the name or pseudonym that you have chosen for attribution should I choose to quote any part of your response in the body of my dissertation, and a contact e-mail address if you choose to participate in a follow-up interview. By continuing with this survey you are agreeing to these terms.

All questions are optional - please skip any that you feel do not apply to you.

- 1) Name or Pseudonym:

- 2) Please describe briefly why you read/write fanfiction.

- 3) Which aspect of a book/movie/TV show is most likely to inspire you to write fanfiction?
 - * Exciting/intriguing plot
 - * Well-rounded genuine characters
 - * Exploration of social/political issues
 - * Standard of acting/directing/writing
 - * Other (Please Specify):

- 4) Have you ever purchased an official novelisation/series tie-in for any of the fandoms in which you participate?

Please Select: Yes/No

5) If you answered 'Yes' to the previous question, on a scale of 1 to 5, 1 being dreadful and 5 being excellent, how would you rate the average quality of any official novelisations you have read and/or purchased?

1 Dreadful

2 Poor

3 Average

4 Quite good

5 Excellent

6) Have you ever felt anger or dissatisfaction at the direction a book/movie/TV show has taken or the way particular characters are portrayed?

Please Select: Yes/No

7) Fandom in general has a tendency to get possessive over characters or 'ships'. Do you agree?

Please Select: Yes/No

8) If you answered 'True' to the previous question, why do you think this is?

9) Do you believe you write characters as the authors/creators intended them or as you yourself have personally interpreted them?

* As the authors/created intended them

* As I personally interpret them

10) Where do you publish your fanfiction?

* Online journal or blog

* Fanfiction Archive

- * Fan website
- * Fanzines
- * Other (Please Specify):

11) Would you ever publish your fanfiction on a mainstream 'official' website, such as FanLib.com, for example?

Please Select: Yes/No

12) Do you think it is important for fanfiction to remain low-profile and not-for-profit?

Please Select: Yes/No

13) If you answered 'Yes' to the previous question, please explain why.

14) Would an author's attitude towards fanfiction dissuade you from writing any based upon his/her characters?

Please Select: Yes/No

15) Have you ever had any of your fanfiction plagiarised?

Please Select: Yes/No

16) If you answered 'Yes' the previous question, please explain how you reacted to the plagiarism.

17) Have you ever participated in a fanfiction remix challenge?

- * I have read remixes but never written any.
- * I have both read and written remixes.
- * I have never read or written a fanfiction remix, although I am aware of them.

* I do not know what a remix challenge is.

18) How do you feel about fanfiction writers who break the 'rules of engagement', i.e. draw the attention of actors or writers to the existence of fanfiction; try and make money from their fanfiction; plagiarise other writers etc.?

19) Do you believe that writing fanfiction containing copyrighted characters is illegal under copyright law?

Please Select: Yes/No

20) If you answered 'No' to the previous question, please explain why not.

21) Do you believe that posting a disclaimer stating that you do not own the characters, fictional world or trademarks contained within your fanfiction ought to protect you from legal action?

Please Select: Yes/No

22) Have you or anyone you know ever been involved in a legal dispute over fanfiction and/or a fan website? (i.e. Cease & Desist letters etc.)

Please Select: Yes/No

23) If you answered 'Yes' to the previous question, please describe briefly what the situation was and what the eventual outcome was.

24) Are you familiar with Creative Commons? If 'No' please skip the next question.

Please Select: Yes/No

25) Do you think that Creative Commons allows a more flexible approach to intellectual property use than current copyright law?

Please Select: Yes/No

26) Do you believe that copyright law needs to evolve and adapt to the current online situation?

Please Select: Yes/No

27) Please rate the following statements from 1 to 5, 1 being complete disagreement and 5 being complete agreement.

1 Completely disagree

2 Partially disagree

3 Neutral

4 Partially agree

5 Completely agree

* I believe writing fanfic is an expression of love for a show/movie/book.

* I believe TV shows/movies/books benefit from having a large and passionate fan base.

* I believe fanfiction does no harm to the original product.

* I believe there is no danger of my unofficial fanfiction being confused with official publications.

* I believe it is wrong for me to profit from my fanfiction.

* I believe writing/reading fanfiction has had a beneficial effect on my own literacy.

* I believe that my interpretation of a character can differ significantly from what the author/creator may have intended.

* I believe that once a work of fiction has entered the public consciousness to such an extent that it becomes a part of culture it is therefore fair game for use.

28) Would you agree to participate in a brief follow-up interview via e-mail or IM? If 'Yes', please list the e-mail address through which you would prefer to be contacted:

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